

Supplementary Material: Mixed model analyses for “Predicting subjective affective ratings of bitter and sweet liquid solutions using facial electromyography during emptying, swirling, and while thinking about the taste.”

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Model Naming

LMTEModX

^	^	
		Null = Random effects (RE) only, 1 = +(1 ptp), 3= (1 ptp)+(1 content)+(1 concentration*)
TE	Tasting Block	Emptying
TS	Tasting Block	Swirling
TT	Tasting Block	Thinking
RE	Tasting and Rating Block	Emptying
RS	Tasting and Rating Block	Swirling
RT	Tasting and Rating Block	Thinking

**Note: the concentration variable is called intensity in the dataset. This is just a naming convention that slipped in at the start of the project. There is a labelled magnitude scale LMS dependent variable also within the data called LMS.*

Markdown

```
library("lme4")

## Warning: package 'lme4' was built under R version 3.3.3

## Loading required package: Matrix

library("ggplot2")
library("lattice")

# open existing dataframes from Liquids data.
load("H:/cannon/Research/LiquidsEMG/data/processed/liquidsEmptyingTasting.Rda")
load("H:/cannon/Research/LiquidsEMG/data/processed/liquidsSwirlingTasting.Rda")
load("H:/cannon/Research/LiquidsEMG/data/processed/liquidsThinkingTasting.Rda")
load("H:/cannon/Research/LiquidsEMG/data/processed/liquidsEmptyingRating.Rda")
load("H:/cannon/Research/LiquidsEMG/data/processed/liquidsSwirlingRating.Rda")
load("H:/cannon/Research/LiquidsEMG/data/processed/liquidsThinkingRating.Rda")

# data is ~152 rows: 8 samples x 19 participants

# quick fix to convert the sample number into a factor
```

```

EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting$SampleFact <- as.factor(EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tas
ting$sampleNum)
EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting$SampleFact <- as.factor(EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tas
ting$sampleNum)
EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting$SampleFact <- as.factor(EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tas
ting$sampleNum)
EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating$SampleFact <- as.factor(EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rati
ng$sampleNum)
EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating$SampleFact <- as.factor(EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rati
ng$sampleNum)
EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating$SampleFact <- as.factor(EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rati
ng$sampleNum)

version

##
## platform      _
## arch          x86_64-w64-mingw32
## os            x86_64
## system        mingw32
## status
## major         3
## minor         3.1
## year          2016
## month         06
## day           21
## svn rev       70800
## language      R
## version.string R version 3.3.1 (2016-06-21)
## nickname      Bug in Your Hair

citation("lme4")

##
## To cite lme4 in publications use:
##
## Douglas Bates, Martin Maechler, Ben Bolker, Steve Walker (2015).
## Fitting Linear Mixed-Effects Models Using lme4. Journal of
## Statistical Software, 67(1), 1-48. doi:10.18637/jss.v067.i01.
##
## A BibTeX entry for LaTeX users is
##
## @Article{,
##   title = {Fitting Linear Mixed-Effects Models Using {lme4}},
##   author = {Douglas Bates and Martin M{"a}chler and Ben Bolker and Stev
e Walker},
##   journal = {Journal of Statistical Software},
##   year = {2015},
##   volume = {67},
##   number = {1},
##   pages = {1--48},

```

```

##   doi = {10.18637/jss.v067.i01},
##   }

citation("ggplot2")

##
## To cite ggplot2 in publications, please use:
##
##   H. Wickham. ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis.
##   Springer-Verlag New York, 2009.
##
## A BibTeX entry for LaTeX users is
##
##   @Book{,
##     author = {Hadley Wickham},
##     title = {ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis},
##     publisher = {Springer-Verlag New York},
##     year = {2009},
##     isbn = {978-0-387-98140-6},
##     url = {http://ggplot2.org},
##   }

citation("lattice")

##
## To cite the lattice package in publications use:
##
##   Sarkar, Deepayan (2008) Lattice: Multivariate Data Visualization
##   with R. Springer, New York. ISBN 978-0-387-75968-5
##
## A BibTeX entry for LaTeX users is
##
##   @Book{,
##     title = {Lattice: Multivariate Data Visualization with R},
##     author = {Deepayan Sarkar},
##     publisher = {Springer},
##     address = {New York},
##     year = {2008},
##     note = {ISBN 978-0-387-75968-5},
##     url = {http://lmdvr.r-forge.r-project.org},
##   }

```

1. Null Models (random effects only)
2. Fixed effect models

Null Models: Random effect: ptp

Raw Scores

Tasting Block

```

cat("Null model w random effects")

## Null model w random effects

cat("Tasting Block Emptying Screen")

## Tasting Block Emptying Screen

LMTEModRandomNull <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting,
REML = FALSE)
LMTEModRandomNull

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1323.0533 1332.1051 -658.5266 1317.0533     148
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept)  0.00
## Residual                    18.96
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -6.626

confint(LMTEModRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01         0.000000  5.531553
## .sigma         16.603747 20.927539
## (Intercept)  -9.561549 -3.482357

coef(LMTEModRandomNull)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1      -6.625695
## 2      -6.625695
## 3      -6.625695
## 4      -6.625695
## 5      -6.625695
## 6      -6.625695
## 7      -6.625695

```

```
## 8 -6.625695
## 9 -6.625695
## 10 -6.625695
## 12 -6.625695
## 13 -6.625695
## 14 -6.625695
## 15 -6.625695
## 16 -6.625695
## 17 -6.625695
## 18 -6.625695
## 19 -6.625695
## 20 -6.625695
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTEModRandomNull, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTEModRandomNull)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting Block Swirling Screen
```

```

LMTSMoRandomNull <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting,
REML = FALSE)
LMTSMoRandomNull

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 1323.3213 1332.3731 -658.6606 1317.3213 148
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 0.00
## Residual 18.97
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
## -6.589

confint(LMTSMoRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.000000 5.523588
## .sigma 16.636622 20.966158
## (Intercept) -9.636988 -3.509157

coef(LMTSMoRandomNull)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1 -6.588874
## 2 -6.588874
## 3 -6.588874
## 4 -6.588874
## 5 -6.588874
## 6 -6.588874
## 7 -6.588874
## 8 -6.588874
## 9 -6.588874
## 10 -6.588874
## 12 -6.588874
## 13 -6.588874
## 14 -6.588874
## 15 -6.588874
## 16 -6.588874
## 17 -6.588874
## 18 -6.588874
## 19 -6.588874
## 20 -6.588874
##

```

```
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTSModRandomNull, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTSModRandomNull)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting Block Thinking Screen")

## Tasting Block Thinking Screen

LMTTModRandomNull <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTTModRandomNull

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 1323.3213 1332.3731 -658.6606 1317.3213     148
## Random effects:
## Groups Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp    (Intercept) 0.00
## Residual          18.97
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19
```

```
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -6.589

confint(LMTTModRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      0.00000  5.652603
## .sigma     16.58539 21.022880
## (Intercept) -9.69546 -3.615399

coef(LMTTModRandomNull)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1      -6.588874
## 2      -6.588874
## 3      -6.588874
## 4      -6.588874
## 5      -6.588874
## 6      -6.588874
## 7      -6.588874
## 8      -6.588874
## 9      -6.588874
## 10     -6.588874
## 12     -6.588874
## 13     -6.588874
## 14     -6.588874
## 15     -6.588874
## 16     -6.588874
## 17     -6.588874
## 18     -6.588874
## 19     -6.588874
## 20     -6.588874
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTTModRandomNull, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTTModRandomNull)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

Tasting and Rating Block

```
# Tasting and Rating Block
```

```
cat("Null model w random effects")
```

```
## Null model w random effects
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen
```

```
LMREModRandomNull <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
, REML = FALSE)
```

```
LMREModRandomNull
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
```

```
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1330.0011 1339.0727 -662.0005 1324.0011      149
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 5.148e-07
## Residual                1.885e+01
```

```

## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -6.301

confint(LMREModRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %          97.5 %
## .sig01      3.669790e-07  6.541879e-07
## .sigma      1.662800e+01  2.091976e+01
## (Intercept) -9.320851e+00 -3.300408e+00

coef(LMREModRandomNull)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1  -6.300855
## 2  -6.300855
## 3  -6.300855
## 4  -6.300855
## 5  -6.300855
## 6  -6.300855
## 7  -6.300855
## 8  -6.300855
## 9  -6.300855
## 10 -6.300855
## 12 -6.300855
## 13 -6.300855
## 14 -6.300855
## 15 -6.300855
## 16 -6.300855
## 17 -6.300855
## 18 -6.300855
## 19 -6.300855
## 20 -6.300855
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMREModRandomNull, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(LMREModRandomNull)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen

LMRSMoRandomNull <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
, REML = FALSE)
LMRSMoRandomNull

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1331.1376 1340.2092 -662.5688 1325.1376     149
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 3.953e-07
## Residual                1.892e+01
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -6.55

confint(LMRSMoRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...  
##           2.5 %           97.5 %  
## .sig01      3.487218e-07  4.946343e-07  
## .sigma      1.672630e+01  2.094728e+01  
## (Intercept) -9.669739e+00 -3.543990e+00  
  
coef(LMRModRandomNull)  
  
## $ptp  
## (Intercept)  
## 1 -6.550263  
## 2 -6.550263  
## 3 -6.550263  
## 4 -6.550263  
## 5 -6.550263  
## 6 -6.550263  
## 7 -6.550263  
## 8 -6.550263  
## 9 -6.550263  
## 10 -6.550263  
## 12 -6.550263  
## 13 -6.550263  
## 14 -6.550263  
## 15 -6.550263  
## 16 -6.550263  
## 17 -6.550263  
## 18 -6.550263  
## 19 -6.550263  
## 20 -6.550263  
##  
## attr(,"class")  
## [1] "coef.mer"  
  
qqmath(LMRModRandomNull, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMRModRandomNull)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Rating Block Emptying Thinking")

## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Thinking

LMRModRandomNull <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
, REML = FALSE)
LMRModRandomNull

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 1334.1885 1343.2601 -664.0943 1328.1885     149
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp    (Intercept)  2.609
## Residual                18.940
## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -6.101

confint(LMRModRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
##           2.5 %   97.5 %  
## .sig01      0.000000  6.439560  
## .sigma     16.599604 21.043644  
## (Intercept) -9.296062 -2.888451
```

```
coef(LMRTModRandomNull)
```

```
## $ptp  
## (Intercept)  
## 1   -5.694198  
## 2   -6.318959  
## 3   -4.845309  
## 4   -6.103893  
## 5   -7.502559  
## 6   -5.818458  
## 7   -6.920811  
## 8   -4.643263  
## 9   -6.361807  
## 10  -7.319135  
## 12  -6.386527  
## 13  -5.828017  
## 14  -6.197500  
## 15  -6.156959  
## 16  -3.869852  
## 17  -5.092181  
## 18  -6.912407  
## 19  -7.484925  
## 20  -6.470740  
##  
## attr(,"class")  
## [1] "coef.mer"
```

```
qqmath(LMRTModRandomNull, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMRTModRandomNull)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

standardised scores

Tasting Block

```
cat("Null model w random effects")
```

```
## Null model w random effects
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Emptying Screen
```

```
zLMTEModRandomNull <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTEModRandomNull
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 425.8002 434.8521 -209.9001 419.8002      148
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
```

```

## ptp      (Intercept) 1.072e-09
## Residual                9.715e-01
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -0.01417

confint(zLMTEModRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##                2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01          9.461411e-10 1.190742e-09
## .sigma          8.576391e-01 1.077803e+00
## (Intercept) -1.690971e-01 1.440848e-01

coef(zLMTEModRandomNull)

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)
## 1  -0.01417054
## 2  -0.01417054
## 3  -0.01417054
## 4  -0.01417054
## 5  -0.01417054
## 6  -0.01417054
## 7  -0.01417054
## 8  -0.01417054
## 9  -0.01417054
## 10 -0.01417054
## 12 -0.01417054
## 13 -0.01417054
## 14 -0.01417054
## 15 -0.01417054
## 16 -0.01417054
## 17 -0.01417054
## 18 -0.01417054
## 19 -0.01417054
## 20 -0.01417054
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTEModRandomNull, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMTModRandomNull)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting Block Swirling Screen

zLMTSModRandomNull <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTSModRandomNull

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 426.0682 435.1200 -210.0341  420.0682     148
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp    (Intercept) 1.030e-09
## Residual              9.724e-01
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
## -0.01228

confint(zLMTSModRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...  
##           2.5 %      97.5 %  
## .sig01      9.117613e-10 1.144914e-09  
## .sigma      8.609585e-01 1.079565e+00  
## (Intercept) -1.712811e-01 1.424885e-01  
  
coef(zLMTSModRandomNull)  
  
## $ptp  
## (Intercept)  
## 1 -0.01228345  
## 2 -0.01228345  
## 3 -0.01228345  
## 4 -0.01228345  
## 5 -0.01228345  
## 6 -0.01228345  
## 7 -0.01228345  
## 8 -0.01228345  
## 9 -0.01228345  
## 10 -0.01228345  
## 12 -0.01228345  
## 13 -0.01228345  
## 14 -0.01228345  
## 15 -0.01228345  
## 16 -0.01228345  
## 17 -0.01228345  
## 18 -0.01228345  
## 19 -0.01228345  
## 20 -0.01228345  
##  
## attr(,"class")  
## [1] "coef.mer"  
  
qqmath(zLMTSModRandomNull, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMTSModRandomNull)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting Block Thinking Screen")

## Tasting Block Thinking Screen

zLMTTModRandomNull <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTTModRandomNull

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 426.0682 435.1200 -210.0341  420.0682     148
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp    (Intercept) 1.030e-09
## Residual              9.724e-01
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
## -0.01228

confint(zLMTTModRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...  
##           2.5 %      97.5 %  
## .sig01      9.106606e-10 1.145478e-09  
## .sigma      8.598851e-01 1.078279e+00  
## (Intercept) -1.661548e-01 1.417313e-01  
  
coef(zLMTTModRandomNull)  
  
## $ptp  
## (Intercept)  
## 1 -0.01228345  
## 2 -0.01228345  
## 3 -0.01228345  
## 4 -0.01228345  
## 5 -0.01228345  
## 6 -0.01228345  
## 7 -0.01228345  
## 8 -0.01228345  
## 9 -0.01228345  
## 10 -0.01228345  
## 12 -0.01228345  
## 13 -0.01228345  
## 14 -0.01228345  
## 15 -0.01228345  
## 16 -0.01228345  
## 17 -0.01228345  
## 18 -0.01228345  
## 19 -0.01228345  
## 20 -0.01228345  
##  
## attr(,"class")  
## [1] "coef.mer"  
  
qqmath(zLMTTModRandomNull, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMTTModRandomNull)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

Tasting and Rating Block

```
# Tasting and Rating Block
```

```
cat("Null model w random effects")
```

```
## Null model w random effects
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen
```

```
zLMREModRandomNull <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rati
ng, REML = FALSE)
zLMREModRandomNull
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
```

```
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 426.8059 435.8776 -210.4030 420.8059      149
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
```

```
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.0000
```

```
## Residual                0.9659
```

```

## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##    0.002478

confint(zLMREModRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01         0.0000000 0.2822907
## .sigma         0.8467531 1.0677740
## (Intercept) -0.1457406 0.1536989

coef(zLMREModRandomNull)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1 0.002477569
## 2 0.002477569
## 3 0.002477569
## 4 0.002477569
## 5 0.002477569
## 6 0.002477569
## 7 0.002477569
## 8 0.002477569
## 9 0.002477569
## 10 0.002477569
## 12 0.002477569
## 13 0.002477569
## 14 0.002477569
## 15 0.002477569
## 16 0.002477569
## 17 0.002477569
## 18 0.002477569
## 19 0.002477569
## 20 0.002477569
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMREModRandomNull, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMREModRandomNull)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen

zLMRSMoRandomNull <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rati
ng, REML = FALSE)
zLMRSMoRandomNull

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 427.9425 437.0141 -210.9712 421.9425     149
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp    (Intercept) 2.285e-08
## Residual                9.695e-01
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -0.0103

confint(zLMRSMoRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...  
##           2.5 %      97.5 %  
## .sig01      1.895191e-08 3.022355e-08  
## .sigma      8.563031e-01 1.074188e+00  
## (Intercept) -1.629757e-01 1.434630e-01  
  
coef(zLMRSMoRandomNull)  
  
## $ptp  
## (Intercept)  
## 1 -0.01030463  
## 2 -0.01030463  
## 3 -0.01030463  
## 4 -0.01030463  
## 5 -0.01030463  
## 6 -0.01030463  
## 7 -0.01030463  
## 8 -0.01030463  
## 9 -0.01030463  
## 10 -0.01030463  
## 12 -0.01030463  
## 13 -0.01030463  
## 14 -0.01030463  
## 15 -0.01030463  
## 16 -0.01030463  
## 17 -0.01030463  
## 18 -0.01030463  
## 19 -0.01030463  
## 20 -0.01030463  
##  
## attr(,"class")  
## [1] "coef.mer"  
  
qqmath(zLMRSMoRandomNull, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMRModRandomNull)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Thinking")

## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Thinking

zLMRTModRandomNull <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rati
ng, REML = FALSE)
zLMRTModRandomNull

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 430.9934 440.0650 -212.4967 424.9934      149
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp    (Intercept) 0.1337
## Residual                0.9707
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      0.0127

confint(zLMRTModRandomNull, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
##           2.5 %   97.5 %  
## .sig01      0.0000000 0.3367158  
## .sigma      0.8508528 1.0766609  
## (Intercept) -0.1550751 0.1824444
```

```
coef(zLMRTModRandomNull)
```

```
## $ptp  
## (Intercept)  
## 1  0.033568831  
## 2  0.001549774  
## 3  0.077074546  
## 4  0.012571897  
## 5 -0.059109913  
## 6  0.027200493  
## 7 -0.029295280  
## 8  0.087429430  
## 9 -0.000646205  
## 10 -0.049709435  
## 12 -0.001913116  
## 13  0.026710621  
## 14  0.007774528  
## 15  0.009852262  
## 16  0.127066844  
## 17  0.064422331  
## 18 -0.028864530  
## 19 -0.058206183  
## 20 -0.006229058  
##  
## attr(,"class")  
## [1] "coef.mer"
```

```
qqmath(zLMRTModRandomNull, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMRTModRandomNull)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

Null Models: Random effects: ptp + content + intensity (concentration)

Raw Scores

Tasting Block

```
cat("Tasting Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Emptying Screen
```

```
LMTEModRandomNull13 <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity),
data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTEModRandomNull13
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1258.0157 1273.1021 -624.0079 1248.0157      146
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups      Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp         (Intercept)  4.313
## intensity   (Intercept)  7.659
## content     (Intercept) 10.684
## Residual                    13.850
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##          -6.672
```

```
confint(LMTEModRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
##           2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      0.00000  7.042343
## .sig02      0.00000 12.770484
## .sig03      0.00000 17.390316
## .sigma     12.13148 15.483848
## (Intercept) -23.27935 10.338953
```

```
coef(LMTEModRandomNull3)
```

```
## $ptp
##      (Intercept)
## 1      -5.073264
## 2      -7.143651
## 3      -2.260138
## 4      -7.443287
## 5     -11.065971
## 6      -5.485048
## 7      -9.138125
## 8      -1.590580
## 9      -7.285645
## 10     -10.458126
## 12     -7.367565
## 13     -5.516723
## 14     -6.741152
## 15     -6.606803
## 16     -2.753295
## 17     -3.078244
## 18     -9.110272
## 19    -11.007535
## 20     -7.646639
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)
## High    -17.2953881
## Low      0.1646108
## Medium  -6.6253484
## Water   -2.9327300
```

```
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)
## Bitter  -16.664929
## Sweet   3.320501
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTEModRandomNull3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTEModRandomNull3)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting Block Swirling Screen

LMTSMoRandomNull3 <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), d
ata = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTSMoRandomNull3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC  logLik deviance df.resid
```

```
## 1258.746 1273.832 -624.373 1248.746      146
## Random effects:
## Groups      Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp         (Intercept)  4.352
## intensity   (Intercept)  7.676
## content     (Intercept) 10.656
## Residual                    13.879
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##          -6.641
```

```
confint(LMTSMoRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
##              2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01         0.000000e+00  7.187433
## .sig02         1.373048e-09 12.619043
## .sig03         0.000000e+00 17.929178
## .sigma         1.216542e+01 15.586298
## (Intercept) -2.283825e+01 10.619500
```

```
coef(LMTSMoRandomNull3)
```

```
## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1      -5.043661
## 2      -7.129848
## 3      -2.209066
## 4      -6.411707
## 5     -11.082103
## 6      -5.458587
## 7      -9.139544
## 8      -1.534398
## 9      -7.272926
## 10     -10.469619
## 12     -7.355471
## 13     -5.490505
## 14     -6.724277
## 15     -6.588903
## 16     -2.705987
## 17     -3.033415
## 18     -9.111479
## 19    -11.023221
## 20     -8.396723
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)
## High    -17.2931509
## Low      0.1672179
```

```
## Medium -6.6228851
## Water -2.8156956
##
## $content
## (Intercept)
## Bitter -16.601361
## Sweet 3.319104
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTSModRandomNull13, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTSModRandomNull13)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting Block Thinking Screen")

## Tasting Block Thinking Screen

LMTTModRandomNull13 <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTTModRandomNull13

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
```

```

## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 1258.746 1273.832 -624.373 1248.746 146
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 4.352
## intensity (Intercept) 7.676
## content (Intercept) 10.656
## Residual 13.879
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
## -6.641

confint(LMTTModRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.000000e+00 7.060576
## .sig02 4.211765e-07 12.769658
## .sig03 0.000000e+00 17.576126
## .sigma 1.216912e+01 15.561261
## (Intercept) -2.370978e+01 10.304177

coef(LMTTModRandomNull3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1 -5.043661
## 2 -7.129848
## 3 -2.209066
## 4 -6.411707
## 5 -11.082103
## 6 -5.458587
## 7 -9.139544
## 8 -1.534398
## 9 -7.272926
## 10 -10.469619
## 12 -7.355471
## 13 -5.490505
## 14 -6.724277
## 15 -6.588903
## 16 -2.705987
## 17 -3.033415
## 18 -9.111479
## 19 -11.023221
## 20 -8.396723
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)

```

```
## High    -17.2931509
## Low     0.1672179
## Medium  -6.6228851
## Water   -2.8156956
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)
## Bitter  -16.601361
## Sweet    3.319104
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTTModRandomNull13, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTTModRandomNull13)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

Tasting and Rating Block

```
# Tasting and Rating Block
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen")

## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen
```

```

LMREModRandomNull3 <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), d
ata = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating, REML = FALSE)
LMREModRandomNull3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1270.2043 1285.3237 -630.1021 1260.2043     147
## Random effects:
## Groups      Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept)  4.244
## intensity (Intercept)  7.473
## content  (Intercept) 10.317
## Residual                    14.076
## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -6.301

confint(LMREModRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      0.00000  7.054068
## .sig02      0.00000 12.482952
## .sig03      0.00000 16.779826
## .sigma     12.38889 15.784404
## (Intercept) -23.05010 10.082549

coef(LMREModRandomNull3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1 -4.916209
## 2 -4.916209
## 3 -2.205007
## 4 -6.224702
## 5 -10.691788
## 6 -5.313073
## 7 -8.833792
## 8 -1.559709
## 9 -7.048431
## 10 -10.105967
## 12 -7.127383
## 13 -5.343601
## 14 -6.523665
## 15 -6.394184
## 16 -2.680297
## 17 -2.993472

```

```
## 18 -8.806948
## 19 -10.635470
## 20 -7.396345
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)
## High -16.8829594
## Low  -0.1277255
## Medium -5.6184552
## Water -2.5742809
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)
## Bitter -15.931103
## Sweet  3.329393
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMREModRandomNull3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMREModRandomNull3)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen")
```

```

## Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen

LMRSMoRandomNull3 <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), d
ata = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating, REML = FALSE)
LMRSMoRandomNull3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 1266.8355 1281.9549 -628.4178 1256.8355 147
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 4.256
## intensity (Intercept) 7.730
## content (Intercept) 10.571
## Residual 13.891
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
## -6.55

confint(LMRSMoRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.00000 7.007088
## .sig02 0.00000 12.904674
## .sig03 0.00000 17.258136
## .sigma 12.14596 15.519790
## (Intercept) -22.64924 10.613507

coef(LMRSMoRandomNull3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1 -5.032761
## 2 -7.065419
## 3 -2.270898
## 4 -6.365704
## 5 -10.916263
## 6 -5.437041
## 7 -9.023548
## 8 -1.613542
## 9 -7.204826
## 10 -10.319495
## 12 -7.285253
## 13 -5.468139
## 14 -6.670255
## 15 -6.538354

```

```
## 16 -2.755069
## 17 -3.074096
## 18 -8.996203
## 19 -10.858892
## 20 -7.559241
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)
## High -17.2962738
## Low 0.1808797
## Medium -6.6157506
## Water -2.4699080
##
## $content
## (Intercept)
## Bitter -16.417765
## Sweet 3.317239
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"
```

```
qqmath(LMRModRandomNull13, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMRModRandomNull13)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

```

cat("Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen")

## Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen

LMRTModRandomNull3 <- lmer(LAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), d
ata = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating, REML = FALSE)
LMRTModRandomNull3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 1280.1378 1295.2572 -635.0689 1270.1378 147
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 5.334
## intensity (Intercept) 7.097
## content (Intercept) 10.067
## Residual 14.406
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
## -6.101

confint(LMRTModRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 4.919549e-07 8.263195
## .sig02 0.000000e+00 11.692780
## .sig03 0.000000e+00 16.411945
## .sigma 1.259051e+01 16.166229
## (Intercept) -2.196354e+01 10.269644

coef(LMRTModRandomNull3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1 -4.4858147
## 2 -6.9643546
## 3 -1.1181125
## 4 -6.1111511
## 5 -11.6599161
## 6 -4.9787767
## 7 -9.3520169
## 8 -0.3165588
## 9 -7.1343415
## 10 -10.9322414
## 12 -7.2324109
## 13 -5.0166969
## 14 -6.4825071

```

```
## 15 -6.3216733
## 16  2.7517049
## 17 -2.0974986
## 18 -9.3186733
## 19 -11.5899600
## 20 -7.5665005
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)
## High  -15.81530307
## Low   0.09837839
## Medium -6.21030371
## Water -2.47856108
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)
## Bitter -15.491338
## Sweet  3.288443
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"
```

```
qqmath(LMRTModRandomNull13, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMRTModRandomNull13)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

standardised score (zscore)

Tasting Block

```
# standardised null models (Zscore)
```

```
# Tasting Block
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Emptying Screen
```

```
zLMTEModRandomNull3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity)
, data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
```

```
zLMTEModRandomNull3
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
```

```
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 360.7627 375.8491 -175.3813  350.7627     146
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
```

```
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2211
```

```
## intensity (Intercept) 0.3925
```

```
## content  (Intercept) 0.5476
```

```
## Residual                    0.7098
```

```
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
```

```
## Fixed Effects:
```

```
## (Intercept)
```

```
##      -0.01655
```

```
confint(zLMTEModRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
##           2.5 %    97.5 %
```

```
## .sig01      0.0000000 0.3682004
```

```
## .sig02      0.0000000 0.6505113
```

```
## .sig03      0.0000000 0.9087635
```

```
## .sigma      0.6249728 0.7943598
```

```
## (Intercept) -0.8729032 0.8322791
```

```
coef(zLMTEModRandomNull3)
```

```
## $ptp
```

```
## (Intercept)
```

```
## 1  0.06539180
```

```
## 2 -0.04071584
```

```
## 3  0.20956495
```

```
## 4 -0.05607225
## 5 -0.24173537
## 6 0.04428782
## 7 -0.14293295
## 8 0.24387990
## 9 -0.04799307
## 10 -0.21058322
## 12 -0.05219147
## 13 0.04266444
## 14 -0.02008769
## 15 -0.01320231
## 16 0.18429057
## 17 0.16763690
## 18 -0.14150550
## 19 -0.23874051
## 20 -0.06649403
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)
## High -0.56099399
## Low  0.33383373
## Medium -0.01415276
## Water 0.17509452
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)
## Bitter -0.5286829
## Sweet  0.4955736
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTEModRandomNull3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMTEModRandomNull3)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting Block Swirling Screen

zLMTSModRandomNull3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity),
data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTSModRandomNull3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 361.4929 376.5793 -175.7465 351.4929     146
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2230
## intensity (Intercept) 0.3934
## content  (Intercept) 0.5461
## Residual                    0.7113
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -0.01496
```

```

confint(zLMTSModRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      0.0000000 0.3690033
## .sig02      0.0000000 0.6486890
## .sig03      0.0000000 0.9026382
## .sigma      0.6242742 0.7953672
## (Intercept) -0.8847724 0.8810599

coef(zLMTSModRandomNull3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1  0.066908969
## 2 -0.040008458
## 3  0.212182424
## 4 -0.003203593
## 5 -0.242562127
## 6  0.045643936
## 7 -0.143005673
## 8  0.246759255
## 9 -0.047341228
## 10 -0.211172231
## 12 -0.051571672
## 13  0.044008165
## 14 -0.019222875
## 15 -0.012284947
## 16  0.186715150
## 17  0.169934388
## 18 -0.141567322
## 19 -0.239544410
## 20 -0.104935969
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)
## High -0.56087931
## Low  0.33396734
## Medium -0.01402651
## Water 0.18109255
##
## $content
## (Intercept)
## Bitter -0.525425
## Sweet  0.495502
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTSModRandomNull3, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMTSModRandomNull3)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting Block Thinking Screen")

## Tasting Block Thinking Screen

zLMTTModRandomNull3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity),
data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTTModRandomNull3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 361.4929 376.5793 -175.7465  351.4929     146
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2230
## intensity (Intercept) 0.3934
## content  (Intercept) 0.5461
## Residual                    0.7113
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -0.01496
```

```

confint(zLMTTModRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      0.0000000 0.3697321
## .sig02      0.0000000 0.6488590
## .sig03      0.0000000 0.8863322
## .sigma      0.6256480 0.7940762
## (Intercept) -0.8883188 0.8120561

coef(zLMTTModRandomNull3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1  0.066908969
## 2 -0.040008458
## 3  0.212182424
## 4 -0.003203593
## 5 -0.242562127
## 6  0.045643936
## 7 -0.143005673
## 8  0.246759255
## 9 -0.047341228
## 10 -0.211172231
## 12 -0.051571672
## 13  0.044008165
## 14 -0.019222875
## 15 -0.012284947
## 16  0.186715150
## 17  0.169934388
## 18 -0.141567322
## 19 -0.239544410
## 20 -0.104935969
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)
## High -0.56087931
## Low  0.33396734
## Medium -0.01402651
## Water 0.18109255
##
## $content
## (Intercept)
## Bitter -0.525425
## Sweet  0.495502
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTTModRandomNull3, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMTTModRandomNull3)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

Tasting and Rating Block

```
# Tasting and Rating Block
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen
```

```
zLMREModRandomNull3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity),
data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMREModRandomNull3
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 367.0091 382.1285 -178.5046 357.0091      147
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2175
## intensity (Intercept) 0.3830
## content  (Intercept) 0.5287
## Residual                0.7214
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
```

```

## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
## 0.002478

confint(zLMREModRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %   97.5 %
## .sig01      0.0000000 0.3657460
## .sig02      0.0000000 0.6308545
## .sig03      0.0000000 0.8704872
## .sigma      0.6347294 0.8095877
## (Intercept) -0.8514248 0.8321266

coef(zLMREModRandomNull3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1 0.0734440928
## 2 0.0734440928
## 3 0.212390430
## 4 0.006380461
## 5 -0.222558469
## 6 0.053101591
## 7 -0.127335843
## 8 0.245462084
## 9 -0.035835802
## 10 -0.192535018
## 12 -0.039882089
## 13 0.051537026
## 14 -0.008941480
## 15 -0.002305569
## 16 0.188031781
## 17 0.171981509
## 18 -0.125960106
## 19 -0.219672117
## 20 -0.053666441
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)
## High -0.53985694
## Low 0.31885144
## Medium 0.03745068
## Water 0.19346509
##
## $content
## (Intercept)
## Bitter -0.4910742
## Sweet 0.4960293
##

```

```
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMREModRandomNull3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMREModRandomNull3)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen

zLMRSMoRandomNull3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity),
data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMRSMoRandomNull3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 363.6404 378.7598 -176.8202  353.6404     147
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2181
## intensity (Intercept) 0.3962
## content  (Intercept) 0.5417
```

```

## Residual                0.7119
## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
##      -0.0103

confint(zLMRModRandomNull3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##                2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01          0.000000e+00 0.3604610
## .sig02          5.066221e-09 0.6490852
## .sig03          0.000000e+00 0.8926206
## .sigma          6.251029e-01 0.7925319
## (Intercept) -8.618135e-01 0.8241395

coef(zLMRModRandomNull3)

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)
## 1  0.0674675889
## 2 -0.0367064509
## 3  0.2090134816
## 4 -0.0008459597
## 5 -0.2340628091
## 6  0.0467481941
## 7 -0.1370608675
## 8  0.2427031078
## 9 -0.0438510698
## 10 -0.2034783442
## 12 -0.0479729653
## 13  0.0451543944
## 14 -0.0164542042
## 15 -0.0096942955
## 16  0.1841996705
## 17  0.1678494849
## 18 -0.1356594230
## 19 -0.2311225236
## 20 -0.0620148895
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)
## High  -0.56103936
## Low   0.33466751
## Medium -0.01366087
## Water  0.19881422
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)
## Bitter -0.5160157

```

```
## Sweet    0.4954064
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMRModRandomNull13, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMRModRandomNull13)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value

cat("Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen")

## Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen

zLMRTModRandomNull13 <- lmer(zLAM ~ 1 + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity),
data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMRTModRandomNull13

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 376.9427 392.0621 -183.4714 366.9427     147
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name                Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2733
```

```
## intensity (Intercept) 0.3637
## content (Intercept) 0.5159
## Residual 0.7383
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)
## 0.0127
```

```
confint(zLMRTModRandomNull13, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
##           2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      7.706140e-09 0.4211438
## .sig02      0.000000e+00 0.5964380
## .sig03      0.000000e+00 0.8363462
## .sigma      6.514571e-01 0.8253710
## (Intercept) -7.964045e-01 0.8329655
```

```
coef(zLMRTModRandomNull13)
```

```
## $ptp
## (Intercept)
## 1 0.095498695
## 2 -0.031526883
## 3 0.268093988
## 4 0.012199938
## 5 -0.272175184
## 6 0.070234310
## 7 -0.153894969
## 8 0.309173746
## 9 -0.040238741
## 10 -0.234881734
## 12 -0.045264812
## 13 0.068290895
## 14 -0.006832119
## 15 0.001410638
## 16 0.466422767
## 17 0.217900288
## 18 -0.152186105
## 19 -0.268589919
## 20 -0.062386962
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)
## High -0.48513939
## Low 0.33043931
## Medium 0.00711835
## Water 0.19837075
##
## $content
```

```
##      (Intercept)
## Bitter  -0.4685361
## Sweet   0.4939306
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMRTModRandomNull3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMRTModRandomNull3)
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

Full models: random effect (ptp) + fixed effects (muscle activity)

Run mixed model analysis of muscles predicting affect rating (LAM) with participant as random intercept

Model names: LM = linear model; TE/TS/TT/RE/RS/RT = Tasting/Rating block, Emptying/Swirling/Thinking phase; Mod = Model; RI = Random Intercept

DV= Labelled Affective Magnitude (LAM)

Raw scores

Tasting Block

```

# Tasting Block
cat("Tasting Block Emptying Screen")

## Tasting Block Emptying Screen

LMTEModRI <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Emptyin
g.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTEModRI

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
## AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1293.4717 1311.5754 -640.7358 1281.4717    145
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept)  5.913
## Residual                    16.095
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)          corr          zygo          lev
##      2.409         -11.226          8.526         -5.024

confint(LMTEModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01         0.000000  8.769436
## .sigma        14.050990 17.927629
## (Intercept)  -3.479499  8.166204
## corr         -15.631962 -7.028030
## zygo          1.667128 15.539454
## lev          -7.967588 -1.968151

coef(LMTEModRI)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)          corr          zygo          lev
## 1    4.8304200 -11.22554  8.526026 -5.023575
## 2   -0.6221946 -11.22554  8.526026 -5.023575
## 3    4.1846135 -11.22554  8.526026 -5.023575
## 4    2.3458835 -11.22554  8.526026 -5.023575
## 5    2.0843386 -11.22554  8.526026 -5.023575
## 6    1.5917393 -11.22554  8.526026 -5.023575
## 7   -4.0502241 -11.22554  8.526026 -5.023575
## 8    8.9234411 -11.22554  8.526026 -5.023575
## 9   -3.4396032 -11.22554  8.526026 -5.023575

```

```
## 10  4.5690651 -11.22554 8.526026 -5.023575
## 12 -1.1709078 -11.22554 8.526026 -5.023575
## 13  4.7969120 -11.22554 8.526026 -5.023575
## 14 -0.8662527 -11.22554 8.526026 -5.023575
## 15  1.8349481 -11.22554 8.526026 -5.023575
## 16  9.5077277 -11.22554 8.526026 -5.023575
## 17 11.9816927 -11.22554 8.526026 -5.023575
## 18  0.8028853 -11.22554 8.526026 -5.023575
## 19  1.1411586 -11.22554 8.526026 -5.023575
## 20 -2.6836664 -11.22554 8.526026 -5.023575
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTEModRI, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTEModRI)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 8995.1  8995.1  34.724
## zygo  1   76.4    76.4   0.295
## lev   1 2910.4  2910.4  11.235

cat("Tasting Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting Block Swirling Screen
```

```

LMTSModRI <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Swirlin
g.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTSModRI

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 1289.9532 1308.0569 -638.9766 1277.9532 145
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 3.53
## Residual 16.33
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept) corr zygo lev
## 1.372 -2.828 2.120 -3.848

confint(LMTSModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.0000000 6.5425260
## .sigma 14.2047562 17.9792701
## (Intercept) -3.9746128 6.8164037
## corr -5.5312575 -0.1126341
## zygo -0.6255733 4.7008094
## lev -6.2467849 -1.3820455

coef(LMTSModRI)

## $ptp
## (Intercept) corr zygo lev
## 1 2.77813977 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 2 -0.01238407 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 3 3.21611027 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 4 0.90381959 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 5 -1.12958985 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 6 1.82422804 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 7 3.31119347 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 8 5.42928696 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 9 -0.80040939 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 10 -0.98535089 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 12 -0.05257031 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 13 1.92263769 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 14 0.29260533 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 15 2.38902234 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 16 2.66318826 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 17 4.18864996 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 18 -0.30966410 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105

```

```
## 19  0.31775754 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
## 20  0.11708840 -2.828449 2.120473 -3.848105
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"
```

```
qqmath(LMTSModRI, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTSModRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 9537.6  9537.6 35.7786
## zygo  1  175.1   175.1  0.6568
## lev   1 2727.5  2727.5 10.2319
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Thinking Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Thinking Screen
```

```
LMTTModRI <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Thinkin
g.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
```

```
LMTTModRI
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
```

```

## 1289.0112 1307.1149 -638.5056 1277.0112      145
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept)  3.838
## Residual                    16.223
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)          corr          zygo          lev
##      -0.8616          -2.1346          2.1339          -7.0315

confint(LMTTModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01         0.000000  6.799611
## .sigma        14.138450 17.880310
## (Intercept)  -4.973196  3.322453
## corr         -5.891451  1.555309
## zygo         -1.867646  6.071550
## lev         -11.251680 -2.792440

coef(LMTTModRI)

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)          corr          zygo          lev
## 1  0.78320789 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 2 -1.20085602 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 3  0.15497786 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 4 -2.55371164 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 5 -4.40239854 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 6 -1.11375662 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 7 -0.15640857 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 8  3.86471140 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 9 -2.51581646 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 10 -2.48219207 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 12  0.04508737 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 13  0.87834045 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 14 -2.01941039 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 15 -1.80832499 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 16  0.86633196 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 17  3.45159265 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 18 -2.64687739 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 19 -2.21041434 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
## 20 -3.30522209 -2.134571  2.133925 -7.031472
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTTModRI, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(LMTTModRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr 1 9900.5  9900.5 37.6182
## zygo 1  28.8    28.8  0.1096
## lev  1 2795.0  2795.0 10.6201
```

Tasting and Rating Block

```
# Tasting and Rating Block
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen
```

```
LMREModRI <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.
g.Rating, REML = FALSE)
```

```
LMREModRI
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
```

```
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
```

```
## 1296.8785 1315.0218 -642.4393 1284.8785      146
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
```

```
## ptp      (Intercept) 4.606
```

```
## Residual                16.055
```

```

## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
##      2.657      -6.286      9.352      -5.144

confint(LMREModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      0.000000  7.229379
## .sigma     14.056447 17.836912
## (Intercept) -2.535690  7.802661
## corr       -9.042928 -3.573412
## zygo        4.742779 14.063810
## lev        -7.384714 -2.984435

coef(LMREModRI)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## 1      4.6745952 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 2      2.7852846 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 3      4.0991032 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 4      1.8256180 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 5      5.2315896 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 6      1.9620963 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 7     -3.0156064 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 8      7.5360113 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 9     -1.9471513 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 10     2.8766103 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 12     2.1422728 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 13     4.5907127 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 14     1.0706714 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 15     1.6715111 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 16     6.2881011 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 17     7.8070421 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 18     0.6893529 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 19     1.6368577 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
## 20    -1.4343751 -6.286114  9.351915 -5.143736
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMREModRI, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(LMREModRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1  6372    6372 24.7206
## zygo  1   517     517  2.0059
## lev   1  5470    5470 21.2212
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen
```

```
LMRModRI <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.
g.Rating, REML = FALSE)
```

```
LMRModRI
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
```

```
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1286.1810 1304.3243 -637.0905 1274.1810     146
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
```

```
## ptp (Intercept) 2.89
```

```
## Residual 15.76
```

```
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19
```

```
## Fixed Effects:
```

```

## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
##      3.864      -2.523      1.377      -4.079

confint(LMRModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.000000  5.8212969
## .sigma      13.738175 17.3595881
## (Intercept) -1.305729  8.8815000
## corr        -4.475560 -0.6384451
## zygo        -1.294310  3.9969073
## lev         -6.082078 -2.0593203

coef(LMRModRI)

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## 1      4.745367 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 2      2.640286 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 3      5.263838 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 4      3.815842 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 5      2.641903 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 6      3.986460 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 7      5.892841 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 8      6.679507 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 9      1.849124 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 10     2.362352 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 12     2.464169 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 13     4.381057 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 14     2.833688 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 15     4.558414 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 16     5.201256 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 17     5.121596 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 18     2.761716 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 19     3.025659 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
## 20     3.189079 -2.523298  1.376518 -4.078641
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMRModRI, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(LMRModRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 11510.2 11510.2 46.3335
## zygo  1    7.3    7.3  0.0293
## lev   1  3825.7  3825.7 15.4003
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen
```

```
LMRTModRI <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Thinkin
g.Rating, REML = FALSE)
```

```
LMRTModRI
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1288.1796 1306.3229 -638.0898 1276.1796    146
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 4.992
## Residual                    15.507
## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
```

```

## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
##      0.3895      -2.2540      2.5303      -6.4312

confint(LMRTModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.000000  7.9033094
## .sigma     13.513726 17.1521525
## (Intercept) -3.858101  4.6941488
## corr        -5.015386  0.4880755
## zygo        -1.455889  6.4346974
## lev         -9.737223 -3.1549356

coef(LMRTModRI)

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## 1   2.86986090 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 2  -1.04921253 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 3   1.89955706 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 4  -2.03595266 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 5  -4.58997683 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 6  -0.29939832 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 7   1.88571243 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 8   7.45923295 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 9  -2.90021884 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 10 -0.08404516 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 12  0.11514662 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 13  5.44020241 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 14 -2.16317623 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 15 -0.62021245 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 16  6.02542779 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 17  3.89811905 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 18 -2.82593628 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 19 -1.91944286 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
## 20 -3.70602450 -2.253963  2.530256 -6.431166
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMRTModRI, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(LMRTModRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 11709.3 11709.3 48.6942
## zygo  1   50.3   50.3  0.2091
## lev   1 3691.5  3691.5 15.3517
```

Standardised analyses (ZScore)

Tasting Block

```
# Tasting Block (ZScore)
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Emptying Screen
```

```
zLMTEModRI <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
```

```
zLMTEModRI
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
```

```
##      AIC      BIC  logLik deviance df.resid
## 396.2186 414.3223 -192.1093  384.2186     145
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups  Name          Std.Dev.
```

```

## ptp      (Intercept) 0.3030
## Residual                0.8249
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)          zcorr          zzygo          zlev
##   -0.09869          -0.86326          0.39446          -0.44597

confint(zLMTEModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01        0.00000000  0.4557357
## .sigma        0.71791675  0.9177576
## (Intercept) -0.30845600  0.1096804
## zcorr        -1.20345534 -0.5279360
## zzygo         0.07736745  0.7218057
## zlev         -0.71689236 -0.1813391

coef(zLMTEModRI)

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)          zcorr          zzygo          zlev
## 1  0.025435314 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 2  -0.254012012 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 3  -0.007662358 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 4  -0.101897556 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 5  -0.115301789 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 6  -0.140547569 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 7  -0.429699051 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 8   0.235203270 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 9  -0.398404629 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 10  0.012040819 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 12 -0.282133648 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 13  0.023718016 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 14 -0.266520028 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 15 -0.128083085 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 16  0.265148026 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 17  0.391939124 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 18 -0.180976455 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 19 -0.163639905 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
## 20 -0.359662756 -0.8632622  0.3944611 -0.4459658
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTEModRI, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMTEModRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 23.6262 23.6262  34.724
## zzygo 1  0.2007  0.2007   0.295
## zlev  1  7.6444  7.6444  11.235
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Swirling Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Swirling Screen
```

```
zLMTSModRI <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTSModRI
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 392.7001 410.8038 -190.3501  380.7001     145
## Random effects:
## Groups Name          Std.Dev.
## ptp    (Intercept) 0.1809
## Residual                0.8368
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
```

```

## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
##      0.01229      -0.21751      0.09810      -0.34161

confint(zLMTSModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.00000000  0.33538932
## .sigma      0.72760580  0.92517354
## (Intercept) -0.15208570  0.17824221
## zcorr      -0.42432872 -0.01275327
## zzygo      -0.02332401  0.21898792
## zlev      -0.55208891 -0.13174493

coef(zLMTSModRI)

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## 1  0.08436248 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 2 -0.05865229 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 3  0.10680853 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 4 -0.01169672 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 5 -0.11590926 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 6  0.03547435 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 7  0.11168156 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 8  0.22023417 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 9 -0.09903871 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 10 -0.10851699 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 12 -0.06071184 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 13  0.04051786 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 14 -0.04302154 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 15  0.06442015 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 16  0.07847119 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 17  0.15665134 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 18 -0.07388794 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 19 -0.04173249 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
## 20 -0.05201681 -0.2175123  0.09810482 -0.3416139
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTSModRI, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMTSModRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 25.0511 25.0511 35.7786
## zzygo 1  0.4599  0.4599  0.6568
## zlev  1  7.1641  7.1641 10.2319
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Thinking Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Thinking Screen
```

```
zLMTTModRI <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTTModRI
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 391.7582 409.8619 -189.8791 379.7582     145
## Random effects:
## Groups Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp    (Intercept) 0.1967
## Residual              0.8314
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
```

```

## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
##   -0.37823      -0.16415      0.09873      -0.62422

confint(zLMTTModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.00000000  0.3581576
## .sigma      0.72181466  0.9170251
## (Intercept) -0.64616929 -0.1178441
## zcorr       -0.45442172  0.1285874
## zzygo       -0.08035981  0.2798333
## zlev        -1.00171044 -0.2473112

coef(zLMTTModRI)

## $ptp
##   (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## 1  -0.2939270 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 2  -0.3956106 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 3  -0.3261239 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 4  -0.4649446 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 5  -0.5596901 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 6  -0.3911467 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 7  -0.3420825 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 8  -0.1359994 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 9  -0.4630025 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 10 -0.4612792 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 12 -0.3317558 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 13 -0.2890514 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 14 -0.4375616 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 15 -0.4267434 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 16 -0.2896669 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 17 -0.1571718 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 18 -0.4697194 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 19 -0.4473506 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
## 20 -0.5034597 -0.164152  0.09872716 -0.6242161
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTTModRI, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMTTModRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 26.0043 26.0043 37.6182
## zzygo 1  0.0757  0.0757  0.1096
## zlev  1  7.3414  7.3414 10.6201
```

Tasting and Rating Block (ZScore)

```
# Tasting and Rating Block (ZScore)
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen
```

```
zLMREModRI <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating, REML = FALSE)
```

```
zLMREModRI
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
```

```
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
```

```
## 393.6834 411.8267 -190.8417 381.6834      146
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
```

```
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2361
```

```
## Residual                0.8228
```

```

## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)          zcorr          zzygo          zlev
##      0.1103          -0.4834          0.4327          -0.4566

confint(zLMREModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01        0.00000000  0.3731208
## .sigma        0.71643061  0.9155121
## (Intercept) -0.07584648  0.2924236
## zcorr        -0.69110496 -0.2755076
## zzygo         0.20855746  0.6519836
## zlev         -0.65435819 -0.2609342

coef(zLMREModRI)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)          zcorr          zzygo          zlev
## 1  0.213681371 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 2  0.116853963 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 3  0.184187345 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 4  0.067670918 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 5  0.242227369 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 6  0.074665436 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 7 -0.180442485 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 8  0.360329335 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 9 -0.125684006 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 10 0.121534386 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 12 0.083899516 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 13 0.209382374 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 14 0.028979793 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 15 0.059772899 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 16 0.296373733 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 17 0.374219688 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 18 0.009437173 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 19 0.057996895 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
## 20 -0.099404162 -0.4834123  0.4326713 -0.456633
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMREModRI, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMREModRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 16.7366 16.7366 24.7206
## zzygo 1  1.3581  1.3581  2.0059
## zlev  1 14.3674 14.3674 21.2212
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen
```

```
zLMRSModRI <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMRSModRI
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 382.9859 401.1291 -185.4929  370.9859     146
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.1481
## Residual                    0.8078
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
```

```

## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
##      0.10047      -0.19405      0.06369      -0.36208

confint(zLMRSMoRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.00000000  0.29914671
## .sigma      0.70447455  0.89125249
## (Intercept) -0.05257617  0.26000092
## zcorr       -0.34001169 -0.04633574
## zzygo       -0.05487400  0.17902696
## zlev        -0.54546709 -0.18040690

coef(zLMRSMoRI)

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## 1  0.145645373 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 2  0.037759643 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 3  0.172217096 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 4  0.098007078 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 5  0.037842504 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 6  0.106751281 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 7  0.204453592 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 8  0.244770352 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 9  -0.002787535 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 10 0.023515505 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 12 0.028733649 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 13 0.126974421 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 14 0.047671553 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 15 0.136064024 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 16 0.169009760 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 17 0.164927192 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 18 0.043982964 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 19 0.057510078 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
## 20 0.065885395 -0.1940457  0.06368531 -0.3620796
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMRSMoRI, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMRSMoRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 30.2325 30.2325 46.3335
## zzygo 1  0.0191  0.0191  0.0293
## zlev  1 10.0486 10.0486 15.4003
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen
```

```
zLMRTModRI <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMRTModRI
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 384.9845 403.1278 -186.4922 372.9845     146
## Random effects:
## Groups Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp    (Intercept) 0.2558
## Residual              0.7947
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19
## Fixed Effects:
```

```

## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
##      -0.2463      -0.1733      0.1171      -0.5709

confint(zLMRTModRI, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.00000000  0.40658278
## .sigma      0.69144245  0.87991926
## (Intercept) -0.46807802 -0.03363095
## zcorr       -0.37793772  0.03449792
## zzygo       -0.06028807  0.29823711
## zlev        -0.85478429 -0.27721779

coef(zLMRTModRI)

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## 1  -0.11919589 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 2  -0.32004902 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 3  -0.16892411 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 4  -0.37061960 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 5  -0.50151375 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 6  -0.28162092 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 7  -0.16963365 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 8   0.11601015 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 9  -0.41491338 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 10 -0.27058404 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 12 -0.26037543 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 13  0.01253452 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 14 -0.37713983 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 15 -0.29806270 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 16  0.04252741 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 17 -0.06649749 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 18 -0.41110639 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 19 -0.36464846 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
## 20 -0.45621105 -0.1733334  0.1170636 -0.5709241
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMRTModRI, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMRTModRI)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr  1 30.7553 30.7553 48.6942
## zzygo  1  0.1321  0.1321  0.2091
## zlev   1  9.6961  9.6961 15.3517
```

Full model: random effect (ptp+content+concentration); fixed effects (muscle activity)

Adding random effects (intercept only) for ptp, content, concentration (intensity)

Raw scores

Tasting Block

```
cat("Tasting Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Emptying Screen
```

```
LMTEModRI3 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|inte
nsity) , data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTEModRI3
```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula:
## LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1254.4207 1278.5589 -619.2103 1238.4207     143
## Random effects:
## Groups      Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept)  4.550
## intensity (Intercept)  6.219
## content  (Intercept)  9.244
## Residual                13.417
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
##      -3.664      -5.698      2.123      -1.085

confint(LMTEModRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      0.000000  7.073333
## .sig02      0.000000 10.417831
## .sig03      0.000000 15.256454
## .sigma     11.655901 14.986462
## (Intercept) -18.421340 11.603229
## corr       -9.496432 -1.855730
## zygo       -3.677468  8.269522
## lev        -3.759119  1.499173

coef(LMTEModRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## 1 -2.06105797 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 2 -5.01724676 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 3 -0.01636837 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 4 -3.66282310 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 5 -7.70881616 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 6 -2.75435004 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 7 -7.40628608 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 8  2.26700884 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 9 -6.13370364 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 10 -4.36195617 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 12 -5.28926821 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 13 -2.64310777 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 14 -4.98206099 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 15 -4.02174740 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 16  1.05032195 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482
## 17  2.31936420 -5.697774  2.122933 -1.085482

```

```
## 18 -5.78686030 -5.697774 2.122933 -1.085482
## 19 -7.42279386 -5.697774 2.122933 -1.085482
## 20 -5.99235824 -5.697774 2.122933 -1.085482
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## High  -12.0552100 -5.697774 2.122933 -1.085482
## Low   2.0221291 -5.697774 2.122933 -1.085482
## Medium -3.6736657 -5.697774 2.122933 -1.085482
## Water -0.9509607 -5.697774 2.122933 -1.085482
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## Bitter -12.322316 -5.697774 2.122933 -1.085482
## Sweet  4.993462 -5.697774 2.122933 -1.085482
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTEModRI3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTEModRI3)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 1704.81 1704.81  9.4697
```

```

## zygo 1 10.05 10.05 0.0558
## lev 1 123.41 123.41 0.6855

cat("Tasting Block Swirling Screen")

## Testing Block Swirling Screen

LMTSModRI3 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|inte
nsity) , data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTSModRI3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula:
## LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 1251.8186 1275.9569 -617.9093 1235.8186 143
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 4.457
## intensity (Intercept) 5.310
## content (Intercept) 9.364
## Residual 13.349
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept) corr zygo lev
## -4.893 -1.867 2.429 -1.461

confint(LMTSModRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.00000000 7.1555712
## .sig02 0.00000000 9.0893473
## .sig03 0.00000000 15.2107459
## .sigma 11.57965600 14.8371395
## (Intercept) -20.25868964 10.3602703
## corr -4.28396116 0.5259894
## zygo 0.03106174 4.7753864
## lev -3.64693624 0.7652619

coef(LMTSModRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept) corr zygo lev
## 1 -2.61389936 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 2 -5.71317380 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 3 -0.71478153 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 4 -5.04023290 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 5 -9.73309384 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 6 -4.28711075 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009

```

```

## 7  -5.40965813 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 8   1.78775676 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 9  -6.60745084 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 10 -9.54465392 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 12 -5.76861210 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 13 -3.30798172 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 14 -5.64089665 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 15 -4.20657632 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 16 -3.51783795 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 17 -0.06795918 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 18 -7.41135578 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 19 -8.42540341 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## 20 -6.75135114 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## High   -11.8461186 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## Low     0.1733082  -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## Medium  -4.4087887  -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## Water   -3.4919320  -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## Bitter  -13.775183 -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
## Sweet    3.988418  -1.866633 2.429439 -1.461009
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTSModRI3, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(LMTModRI3)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 1659.08 1659.08  9.3111
## zygo  1  569.01  569.01  3.1934
## lev   1  321.22  321.22  1.8028
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Thinking Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Thinking Screen
```

```
LMTTModRI3 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|inte
nsity) , data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTTModRI3
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula:
```

```
## LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
```

```
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1248.3665 1272.5047 -616.1832 1232.3665     143
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 4.163
## intensity (Intercept) 5.057
## content  (Intercept) 9.392
## Residual                          13.249
```

```

## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
##      -4.806      -1.248      3.519      -3.659

confint(LMTTModRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.0000000  6.8337721
## .sig02      0.0000000  8.6853539
## .sig03      0.0000000 15.1198872
## .sigma     11.4614202 14.7942206
## (Intercept) -19.0762732  9.9925689
## corr       -4.3320159  1.8749067
## zygo       0.2774492  6.8885058
## lev       -7.7152111  0.3402745

coef(LMTTModRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## 1  -2.7276329 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 2  -5.7236138 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 3  -1.5268849 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 4  -5.6921413 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 5  -9.3557432 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 6  -4.2926366 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 7  -5.3942813 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 8   1.2238366 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 9  -6.2480584 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 10 -8.3773783 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 12 -4.6551042 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 13 -2.7810021 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 14 -5.6452901 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 15 -5.4080181 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 16 -2.5013404 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 17 -0.3939288 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 18 -7.1021421 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 19 -7.4203248 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## 20 -7.2882037 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## High  -11.4265885 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## Low   -0.1002609 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## Medium -4.1653100 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
## Water  -3.5309751 -1.248468  3.519056 -3.659037
##
## $content

```

```
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## Bitter -13.748559 -1.248468 3.519056 -3.659037
## Sweet   4.136992 -1.248468 3.519056 -3.659037
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTTModRI3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTTModRI3)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 2077.85  2077.85  11.8380
## zygo  1   512.22   512.22   2.9183
## lev   1   620.52   620.52   3.5352
```

Tasting and Rating Block

```
#Tasting and Rating Block
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen
```

```
LMREModRI3 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|inte
nsity) , data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating, REML = FALSE)
LMREModRI3
```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula:
## LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1263.5313 1287.7224 -623.7657 1247.5313     144
## Random effects:
## Groups      Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept)  4.123
## intensity (Intercept)  6.414
## content  (Intercept)  8.195
## Residual                13.555
## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
##      -1.345      -2.894      4.987      -2.908

confint(LMREModRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.0000000  6.5602257
## .sig02      0.0000000 10.7593821
## .sig03      0.0000000 13.7101221
## .sigma      11.8082910 15.0945436
## (Intercept) -15.4380108 12.3951476
## corr        -5.4282135 -0.3360784
## zygo         0.5344272  9.4774752
## lev         -4.9171200 -0.9023596

coef(LMREModRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## 1      0.4435105 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 2     -0.6292372 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 3      1.4022234 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 4     -1.9536348 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 5     -1.6842454 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 6     -1.2529448 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 7     -5.8010454 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 8      3.6200861 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 9     -4.3516607 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 10    -3.4117648 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 12    -2.0924392 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 13     0.3188690 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 14    -2.3034123 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 15    -1.8017420 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 16     2.6337651 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495
## 17     3.1469605 -2.893545  4.986803 -2.908495

```

```

## 18 -3.7654613 -2.893545 4.986803 -2.908495
## 19 -3.8395943 -2.893545 4.986803 -2.908495
## 20 -4.2287621 -2.893545 4.986803 -2.908495
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## High -10.3391118 -2.893545 4.986803 -2.908495
## Low   4.2867310 -2.893545 4.986803 -2.908495
## Medium -0.4993644 -2.893545 4.986803 -2.908495
## Water  1.1726863 -2.893545 4.986803 -2.908495
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## Bitter -8.890449 -2.893545 4.986803 -2.908495
## Sweet  6.200920 -2.893545 4.986803 -2.908495
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMREModRI3, id = 0.05)

```



```

anova(LMREModRI3)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1  876.92   876.92   4.7728

```

```

## zygo 1 69.50 69.50 0.3783
## lev 1 1524.37 1524.37 8.2967

cat("Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen

LMRSMODRI3 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|inte
nsity) , data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating, REML = FALSE)
LMRSMODRI3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula:
## LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 1251.7625 1275.9535 -617.8812 1235.7625 144
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 3.609
## intensity (Intercept) 5.012
## content (Intercept) 8.558
## Residual 13.145
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept) corr zygo lev
## -0.708 -1.139 1.666 -2.812

confint(LMRSMODRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.0000000 6.1696639
## .sig02 0.0000000 8.6167240
## .sig03 0.0000000 13.9507576
## .sigma 11.3690700 14.5517568
## (Intercept) -14.3729490 13.1691225
## corr -2.8493282 0.6485772
## zygo -0.6617022 4.0320215
## lev -4.7815765 -1.0691876

coef(LMRSMODRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept) corr zygo lev
## 1 0.9248390 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 2 -1.9269406 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 3 2.4196085 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 4 -0.8820530 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 5 -3.3730028 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 6 -0.3165256 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569

```

```

## 7    0.1401541 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 8    4.1843223 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 9   -2.8704764 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 10  -4.0758211 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 12  -2.2043306 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 13    0.3270265 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 14  -1.6812196 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 15    0.2788194 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 16    1.3946966 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 17    1.6984628 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 18  -2.7950416 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 19  -3.1708596 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## 20  -1.5238945 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## High    -7.1937417 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## Low      4.0990514 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## Medium  -0.4775662 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## Water    0.7402069 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## Bitter   -8.801499 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
## Sweet     7.385474 -1.139148 1.665652 -2.811569
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"
qqmath(LMRSModRI3, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(LMRModRI3)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 2460.2  2460.2 14.2391
## zygo  1   55.2    55.2  0.3195
## lev   1 1589.2  1589.2  9.1980
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen
```

```
LMRTModRI3 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|inte
nsity) , data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating, REML = FALSE)
```

```
LMRTModRI3
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula:
```

```
## LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
```

```
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1258.7583 1282.9493 -621.3791 1242.7583     144
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept)  5.256
## intensity (Intercept)  3.609
## content  (Intercept)  7.982
## Residual                    13.266
```

```

## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
##      -2.1686      -0.8214      3.1713      -5.2211

confint(LMRTModRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      1.228170e-07  8.057125
## .sig02      0.000000e+00  6.444959
## .sig03      0.000000e+00 12.885757
## .sigma      1.150421e+01 14.733859
## (Intercept) -1.491260e+01 10.316756
## corr        -3.285081e+00  1.588308
## zygo        -3.800014e-01  6.586596
## lev         -8.201571e+00 -2.024517

coef(LMRTModRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## 1      0.4042332 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 2     -3.7111930 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 3      0.9709653 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 4     -4.5391066 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 5     -8.0151338 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 6     -2.2026450 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 7     -2.7979255 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 8      6.3244062 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 9     -4.8963442 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 10    -4.9252050 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 12    -2.6776211 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 13     2.7892222 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 14    -4.3184781 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 15    -2.6375630 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 16     4.8989195 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 17     1.4411764 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 18    -5.7142145 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 19    -5.6908038 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## 20    -5.9064533 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## High      -6.360823 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## Low       1.300053 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## Medium   -1.593456 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
## Water    -2.020251 -0.8213889  3.171295 -5.221102
##
## $content

```

```
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev
## Bitter   -9.760962 -0.8213889 3.171295 -5.221102
## Sweet     5.423724 -0.8213889 3.171295 -5.221102
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMRTModRI3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMRTModRI3)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 3533.8  3533.8 20.0789
## zygo  1  184.9   184.9  1.0504
## lev   1 2055.4  2055.4 11.6787
```

standardised scores

Tasting Block (zscore)

```
#Tasting Block (zscore)
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Emptying Screen
```

```

zLMTEModRI3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1
|intensity) , data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTEModRI3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 |
## intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 357.1676 381.3058 -170.5838 341.1676 143
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 0.2332
## intensity (Intercept) 0.3187
## content (Intercept) 0.4738
## Residual 0.6876
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev
## -0.08644 -0.43817 0.09822 -0.09636

confint(zLMTEModRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.0000000 0.3681537
## .sig02 0.0000000 0.5337862
## .sig03 0.0000000 0.7810677
## .sigma 0.5999360 0.7675441
## (Intercept) -0.8269215 0.6567669
## zcorr -0.7426145 -0.1461338
## zzygo -0.1735306 0.3797299
## zlev -0.3295307 0.1344559

coef(zLMTEModRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev
## 1 -0.004263777 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 2 -0.155768937 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 3 0.100526901 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 4 -0.086354502 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 5 -0.293712310 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 6 -0.039795102 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 7 -0.278207592 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 8 0.217550360 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 9 -0.212987536 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 10 -0.122185178 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 12 -0.169710081 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 13 -0.034093923 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323

```

```
## 14 -0.153965660 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 15 -0.104749428 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 16 0.155194965 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 17 0.220233583 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 18 -0.195211758 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 19 -0.279053620 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## 20 -0.205743560 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## High  -0.51646566 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## Low   0.20500020  -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## Medium -0.08691019 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## Water 0.05262888  -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## Bitter -0.5301549 -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
## Sweet  0.3572815  -0.438168 0.09821861 -0.09636323
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTEModRI3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMTEModRI3)
```

```

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 4.4778  4.4778  9.4697
## zzygo 1 0.0264  0.0264  0.0558
## zlev  1 0.3241  0.3241  0.6855

cat("Tasting Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting Block Swirling Screen

zLMTSModRI3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1
|intensity) , data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTSModRI3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 |
## intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 354.5656 378.7038 -169.2828  338.5656     143
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2284
## intensity (Intercept) 0.2722
## content  (Intercept) 0.4799
## Residual                    0.6841
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## -0.03677      -0.14355      0.11240     -0.12970

confint(zLMTSModRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.00000000 0.36526138
## .sig02      0.00000000 0.46483689
## .sig03      0.00000000 0.79633532
## .sigma      0.591628458 0.76055363
## (Intercept) -0.762403330 0.71368348
## zcorr      -0.325787299 0.04247482
## zzygo      0.005397191 0.22587393
## zlev      -0.321097502 0.06128200

coef(zLMTSModRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## 1  0.080050055 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 2 -0.078788233 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 3  0.177380130 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005

```

```

## 4 -0.044299907 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 5 -0.284809740 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 6 -0.005702281 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 7 -0.063233000 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 8 0.305635598 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 9 -0.124620067 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 10 -0.275152165 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 12 -0.081629454 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 13 0.044478228 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 14 -0.075084017 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 15 -0.001574879 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 16 0.033723069 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 17 0.210529875 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 18 -0.165820314 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 19 -0.217790405 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## 20 -0.131994977 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## High -0.39310261 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## Low 0.22289488 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## Medium -0.01193829 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## Water 0.03505075 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## Bitter -0.4919675 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
## Sweet 0.4184199 -0.1435471 0.1123993 -0.1297005
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"
qqmath(zLMTSModRI3, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMTSModRI3)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr  1  4.3577   4.3577   9.3111
## zzygo  1  1.4945   1.4945   3.1934
## zlev   1  0.8437   0.8437   1.8028
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Thinking Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Thinking Screen
```

```
zLMTTModRI3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTTModRI3
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 351.1134 375.2517 -167.5567  335.1134     143
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2134
## intensity (Intercept) 0.2592
## content  (Intercept) 0.4813
## Residual                    0.6790
```

```

## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)          zcorr          zzygo          zlev
##   -0.17643          -0.09601          0.16281          -0.32483

confint(zLMTTModRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.0000000 0.34900743
## .sig02      0.0000000 0.43392602
## .sig03      0.0000000 0.77378457
## .sigma      0.5861969 0.75280530
## (Intercept) -0.9254135 0.55333751
## zcorr       -0.3331995 0.14000016
## zzygo        0.0110314 0.31405498
## zlev         -0.6635084 0.02094499

coef(zLMTTModRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)          zcorr          zzygo          zlev
## 1  -0.06992202 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 2  -0.22346650 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 3  -0.00838350 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 4  -0.22185353 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 5  -0.40961369 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 6  -0.15012870 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 7  -0.20658816 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 8   0.13259140 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 9  -0.25034437 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 10 -0.35947234 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 12 -0.16870522 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 13 -0.07265720 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 14 -0.21945240 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 15 -0.20729217 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 16 -0.05832449 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 17  0.04968067 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 18 -0.29411629 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 19 -0.31042320 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## 20 -0.30365197 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)          zcorr          zzygo          zlev
## High  -0.51574486 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## Low    0.06473122 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## Medium -0.14360319 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## Water  -0.11109342 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
##
## $content

```

```
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## Bitter -0.6347462 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
## Sweet   0.2818911 -0.09600923 0.162811 -0.3248295
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTTModRI3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMTTModRI3)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 5.4576  5.4576 11.8380
## zzygo 1 1.3454  1.3454  2.9183
## zlev  1 1.6298  1.6298  3.5352
```

Tasting and Rating Block (zscore)

```
#Tasting and Rating Block (zscore)
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen
```

```
zLMREModRI3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMREModRI3
```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 |
## intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 360.3362 384.5273 -172.1681 344.3362     144
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2113
## intensity (Intercept) 0.3287
## content  (Intercept) 0.4200
## Residual                0.6947
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
##      0.0698      -0.2225      0.2307      -0.2582

confint(zLMREModRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.00000000 0.34441605
## .sig02      0.00000000 0.53932645
## .sig03      0.00000000 0.69510460
## .sigma      0.60291059 0.77475778
## (Intercept) -0.61912902 0.75372128
## zcorr      -0.41816580 -0.03031437
## zzygo      0.02667764 0.43404368
## zlev      -0.44843548 -0.07258021

coef(zLMREModRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## 1  0.16145201 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 2  0.10647352 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 3  0.21058620 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 4  0.03859794 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 5  0.05240419 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 6  0.07450841 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 7 -0.15858246 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 8  0.32425201 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 9 -0.08430127 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 10 -0.03613145 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 12  0.03148419 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 13  0.15506412 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 14  0.02067179 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 15  0.04638247 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 16  0.27370291 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 17  0.30000425 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005

```

```
## 18 -0.05425845 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 19 -0.05805778 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## 20 -0.07800269 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## High    -0.3911591 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## Low      0.3584177 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## Medium   0.1131295 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## Water    0.1988224 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## Bitter  -0.3169149 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
## Sweet    0.4565202 -0.2225182 0.2307171 -0.2582005
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMREModRI3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMREModRI3)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 2.3033  2.3033  4.7728
```

```

## zzygo 1 0.1825 0.1825 0.3783
## zlev 1 4.0039 4.0039 8.2967

cat("Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen")

## Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen

zLMRSMoRI3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1
|intensity) , data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMRSMoRI3

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 |
## intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 348.5673 372.7584 -166.2837 332.5673 144
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 0.1850
## intensity (Intercept) 0.2568
## content (Intercept) 0.4386
## Residual 0.6737
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev
## 0.04647 -0.08760 0.07706 -0.24960

confint(zLMRSMoRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.00000000 0.31610454
## .sig02 0.00000000 0.44296048
## .sig03 0.00000000 0.73039329
## .sigma 0.58422990 0.74625364
## (Intercept) -0.62530039 0.72892713
## zcorr -0.22222505 0.04471524
## zzygo -0.02791045 0.18313038
## zlev -0.41849589 -0.08821044

coef(zLMRSMoRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev
## 1 0.130150345 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 2 -0.016003852 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 3 0.206757537 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 4 0.037546825 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 5 -0.090114777 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 6 0.066530198 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959

```

```

## 7  0.089935130 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 8  0.297199426 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 9  -0.064360223 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 10 -0.126134331 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 12 -0.030220138 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 13  0.099512355 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 14 -0.003410607 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 15  0.097041735 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 16  0.154230633 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 17  0.169798700 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 18 -0.060494170 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 19 -0.079754900 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## 20  0.004652337 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## High   -0.28592815 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## Low     0.29282917 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## Medium  0.05827684 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## Water   0.12068788 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## Bitter  -0.3683260 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
## Sweet    0.4612589 -0.08760232 0.07706228 -0.2495959
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"
qqmath(zLMRSMoRI3, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMRSMoRI3)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 6.4620  6.4620 14.2391
## zzygo  1 0.1450  0.1450  0.3195
## zlev   1 4.1743  4.1743  9.1980
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen
```

```
zLMRTModRI3 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMRTModRI3
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 355.5631 379.7542 -169.7816 339.5631     144
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2694
## intensity (Intercept) 0.1850
## content  (Intercept) 0.4091
## Residual                    0.6799
```

```

## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
##   -0.18726      -0.06317      0.14672      -0.46350

confint(zLMRTModRI3, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      1.659578e-09  0.4038004
## .sig02      0.000000e+00  0.3354183
## .sig03      0.000000e+00  0.6380874
## .sigma      5.888976e-01  0.7558848
## (Intercept) -8.178969e-01  0.4624683
## zcorr      -2.498223e-01  0.1210289
## zzygo      -1.890828e-02  0.3099753
## zlev      -7.338582e-01 -0.1909744

coef(zLMRTModRI3)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## 1  -0.055401835  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 2  -0.266318078  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 3  -0.026356729  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 4  -0.308748781  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 5  -0.486895722  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 6  -0.189004755  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 7  -0.219512973  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 8   0.248007971  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 9  -0.327057267  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 10 -0.328536381  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 12 -0.213347352  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 13  0.066829234  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 14 -0.297441537  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 15 -0.211294373  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 16  0.174951546  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 17 -0.002258331  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 18 -0.368973246  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 19 -0.367773442  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## 20 -0.378825516  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## High  -0.402112012  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## Low   -0.009490926  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## Medium -0.157783723  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
## Water -0.179657037  -0.06316612  0.1467216  -0.4635012
##
## $content

```

```
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev
## Bitter -0.5763697 -0.06316612 0.1467216 -0.4635012
## Sweet   0.2018478 -0.06316612 0.1467216 -0.4635012
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMRTModRI3, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMRTModRI3)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 9.2818  9.2818 20.0789
## zzygo 1 0.4856  0.4856  1.0504
## zlev  1 5.3987  5.3987 11.6787
```

Full model + masseter as fixed effect

Raw scores

Tasting Block

```
# adding in Mass as an extra fixed ef
#Tasting Block
```

```

cat("Tasting Block Emptying Screen")

## Tasting Block Emptying Screen

LMTEModRI4 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) +
(1|intensity) , data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTEModRI4

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
## AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1256.148 1283.303 -619.074 1238.148      142
## Random effects:
## Groups      Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp         (Intercept)  4.283
## intensity   (Intercept)  6.376
## content     (Intercept)  9.299
## Residual                    13.445
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## -3.7593      -4.7725      2.4307      -1.1388      -0.6311

confint(LMTEModRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.000000  6.7760699
## .sig02      0.000000 10.7614678
## .sig03      0.000000 15.3317644
## .sigma     11.624841 14.9135991
## (Intercept) -18.844027 11.3457681
## corr       -9.879191  0.2837367
## zygo       -3.673837  8.4104333
## lev        -3.659527  1.5366109
## mass       -2.914732  1.6756136

coef(LMTEModRI4)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## 1 -2.2066853 -4.772462  2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 2 -4.9572842 -4.772462  2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 3 -0.2856734 -4.772462  2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 4 -4.0047505 -4.772462  2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 5 -7.4688678 -4.772462  2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 6 -3.0877398 -4.772462  2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 7 -7.2975064 -4.772462  2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846

```

```

## 8    1.6284057 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 9    -5.9722308 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 10   -3.9217454 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 12   -5.2809457 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 13   -2.7856911 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 14   -4.8730507 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 15   -4.1123333 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 16    0.4708248 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 17    1.5684048 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 18   -5.8771002 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 19   -7.1105718 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## 20   -5.8520810 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## High    -12.369616 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## Low      2.114806  -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## Medium  -3.828351  -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## Water   -0.954023  -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## Bitter  -12.460809 -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
## Sweet    4.942217  -4.772462 2.430708 -1.138768 -0.6310846
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"
qqmath(LMTEModRI4, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(LMTEModRI4)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 1687.12 1687.12  9.3326
## zygo  1   14.32   14.32  0.0792
## lev   1  122.88  122.88  0.6797
## mass  1   54.22   54.22  0.2999
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Swirling Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Swirling Screen
```

```
LMTSMoRI4 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) +
(1|intensity) , data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTSMoRI4
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1252.6834 1279.8390 -617.3417 1234.6834     142
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 4.401
## intensity (Intercept) 5.190
## content  (Intercept) 9.224
```

```
## Residual          13.313
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      corr          zygo          lev          mass
##      -4.436      -1.425      2.860      -1.426      -2.211
```

```
confint(LMTSMoRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
##              2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.000000  7.0311097
## .sig02      0.000000  8.7749807
## .sig03      0.000000 15.0452491
## .sigma      11.4925610 14.7812323
## (Intercept) -18.7280351  9.9204564
## corr        -3.9732761  1.0394370
## zygo         0.3288163  5.3672415
## lev         -3.5817148  0.7143404
## mass        -6.3417301  1.8413092
```

```
coef(LMTSMoRI4)
```

```
## $ptp
## (Intercept)      corr          zygo          lev          mass
## 1  -2.1046371 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 2  -5.5314078 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 3  -0.2312158 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 4  -4.8474529 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 5  -9.2534267 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 6  -4.0152509 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 7  -5.1171797 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 8   1.7835976 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 9  -6.4791354 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 10 -8.8094114 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 12  -5.4818290 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 13  -3.2422219 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 14  -4.9902249 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 15  -3.9149392 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 16  -2.4423547 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 17   0.8007090 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 18  -7.1240731 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 19  -7.1818226 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## 20  -6.1007178 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)      corr          zygo          lev          mass
## High  -11.1622899 -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## Low    0.6148179  -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## Medium -3.8964872  -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## Water  -3.2998290  -1.42532  2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
```

```
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## Bitter -13.185328 -1.42532 2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
## Sweet   4.313434 -1.42532 2.860056 -1.426346 -2.211448
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTSModRI4, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTSModRI4)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 1677.62 1677.62  9.4658
## zygo  1  567.49  567.49  3.2020
## lev   1  326.35  326.35  1.8414
## mass  1  202.42  202.42  1.1421

cat("Tasting Block Thinking Screen")

## Tasting Block Thinking Screen

LMTTModRI4 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) +
(1|intensity) , data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
LMTTModRI4
```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1249.7073 1276.8628 -615.8536 1231.7073     142
## Random effects:
## Groups      Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept)  4.205
## intensity (Intercept)  4.977
## content  (Intercept)  9.395
## Residual                13.213
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
##      -4.591      -1.083      3.768      -3.244      -2.438

confint(LMTTModRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.0000000  6.8679804
## .sig02      0.0000000  8.6759734
## .sig03      0.0000000 15.3581864
## .sigma     11.4537279 14.6800316
## (Intercept) -18.9236756  9.3816175
## corr       -4.2353003  2.2272556
## zygo       0.3670272  7.0741051
## lev       -7.3259568  0.8824485
## mass      -8.6034836  3.3728364

coef(LMTTModRI4)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## 1  -2.5448004 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 2  -4.3918966 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 3  -1.2796203 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 4  -5.5709566 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 5  -9.3242686 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 6  -4.1776483 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 7  -5.4335974 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 8   1.3023173 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 9  -6.3231661 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 10 -8.0618216 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 12 -4.6724054 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 13 -2.7676232 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 14 -5.3153643 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 15 -5.2573579 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 16 -2.1829560 -1.082694  3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176

```

```
## 17  0.2222069 -1.082694 3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 18 -7.0449586 -1.082694 3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 19 -7.2437021 -1.082694 3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## 20 -7.1656395 -1.082694 3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## High  -11.0531955 -1.082694 3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## Low    0.1130223 -1.082694 3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## Medium -3.9451629 -1.082694 3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## Water  -3.4795605 -1.082694 3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## Bitter -13.544471 -1.082694 3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
## Sweet   4.362022 -1.082694 3.768332 -3.243728 -2.438176
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMTTModRI4, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMTTModRI4)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 2084.40  2084.40 11.9384
```

```
## zygo 1 509.07 509.07 2.9157
## lev 1 627.99 627.99 3.5968
## mass 1 115.64 115.64 0.6623
```

Tasting and Rating Block

```
#Tasting and Rating Block
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen
```

```
LMREModRI4 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) +
(1|intensity) , data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating, REML = FALSE)
LMREModRI4
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 1263.1996 1290.4145 -622.5998 1245.1996 143
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 3.684
## intensity (Intercept) 6.675
## content (Intercept) 8.467
## Residual 13.504
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept) corr zygo lev mass
## -1.531 -1.157 6.150 -2.920 -4.063
```

```
confint(LMREModRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.000000 6.0923051
## .sig02 0.000000 11.0992378
## .sig03 0.000000 13.9561976
## .sigma 11.719848 14.9709654
## (Intercept) -15.486736 12.7291972
## corr -4.440908 2.3439689
## zygo 1.677708 10.6334395
## lev -4.884551 -0.9652642
## mass -9.213221 1.0582964
```

```
coef(LMREModRI4)
```

```
## $ptp
## (Intercept) corr zygo lev mass
```

```

## 1  0.08173537 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 2  -1.48868680 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 3  1.01767641 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 4  -2.22216460 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 5  -1.53971827 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 6  -1.66047726 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 7  -5.59390481 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 8  2.46451456 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 9  -4.04303290 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 10 -2.10421519 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 12 -2.12895023 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 13 -0.29391661 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 14 -1.67196568 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 15 -1.89380953 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 16  1.13484486 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 17  2.55371271 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 18 -3.99340992 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 19 -3.88740861 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## 20 -3.81085435 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## High   -11.1065403 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## Low     3.8571129 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## Medium -0.2500544 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## Water  1.3773701 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## Bitter  -9.338081 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
## Sweet   6.277025 -1.157028 6.15012 -2.919717 -4.062995
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMREModRI4, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(LMREModRI4)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1  878.10   878.10  4.8153
## zygo  1   79.11    79.11  0.4338
## lev   1 1509.33 1509.33  8.2769
## mass  1  441.15   441.15  2.4192
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen
```

```
LMRSMoRI4 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) +
(1|intensity) , data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating, REML = FALSE)
LMRSMoRI4
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1253.0335 1280.2484 -617.5167 1235.0335     143
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 3.597
## intensity (Intercept) 4.941
## content  (Intercept) 8.529
```

```
## Residual          13.117
## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      corr          zygo          lev          mass
##      -0.6343      -1.0116       1.8879       -2.6648       -1.1590
```

```
confint(LMRSModRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
##           2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      0.000000  6.1293511
## .sig02      0.000000  8.5787206
## .sig03      0.000000 13.5209807
## .sigma     11.366562 14.5766473
## (Intercept) -14.665760 13.6562014
## corr       -2.807797  0.7366652
## zygo       -0.510907  4.2455981
## lev        -4.541957 -0.7644191
## mass       -3.892699  1.6047629
```

```
coef(LMRSModRI4)
```

```
## $ptp
## (Intercept)      corr          zygo          lev          mass
## 1  1.00992709 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 2 -2.11616678 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 3  2.49472493 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 4 -0.89180643 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 5 -3.40389053 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 6 -0.34431552 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 7 -0.04453451 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 8  4.06618324 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 9 -2.86096482 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 10 -3.94116984 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 12 -2.16424218 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 13  0.21033743 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 14 -1.50748372 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 15  0.34588134 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 16  1.70575685 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 17  2.12617006 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 18 -2.83840699 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 19 -2.51462184 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## 20 -1.38340039 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept)      corr          zygo          lev          mass
## High    -7.0284568 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## Low      4.0837039  -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## Medium  -0.3408113  -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## Water   0.7482963  -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
```

```
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## Bitter  -8.705058 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
## Sweet    7.436424 -1.01162  1.88787 -2.664808 -1.159011
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMRSModRI4, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMRSModRI4)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 2471.07 2471.07 14.3622
## zygo  1   55.15   55.15  0.3205
## lev   1 1593.39 1593.39  9.2610
## mass  1  125.83  125.83  0.7314

cat("Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen")

## Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen

LMRTModRI4 <- lmer(LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) +
(1|intensity) , data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating, REML = FALSE)
LMRTModRI4
```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 1260.6553 1287.8702 -621.3277 1242.6553    143
## Random effects:
## Groups      Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept)  5.287
## intensity (Intercept)  3.650
## content  (Intercept)  7.965
## Residual                13.254
## Number of obs: 152, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## -2.2289      -0.8468      3.0679      -5.3978      0.8130

confint(LMRTModRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##           2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01      0.0000000  7.859409
## .sig02      0.0000000  6.564157
## .sig03      0.0000000 13.032681
## .sigma      11.4564009 14.671169
## (Intercept) -14.3051216  9.871159
## corr        -3.2460621  1.639040
## zygo        -0.6148457  6.640222
## lev         -8.6417336 -2.107433
## mass        -4.1526999  5.718728

coef(LMRTModRI4)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## 1  0.3795220 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 2 -4.3134970 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 3  0.9621724 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 4 -4.6265953 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 5 -8.0502691 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 6 -2.2048840 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 7 -2.7047096 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 8  6.4703359 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 9 -4.9090266 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 10 -5.0481973 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 12 -2.6924206 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 13  2.9247242 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 14 -4.4147386 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 15 -2.6350783 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241
## 16  4.7838599 -0.8467616  3.067857 -5.397824  0.8130241

```

```
## 17  1.1551413 -0.8467616 3.067857 -5.397824 0.8130241
## 18 -5.7457624 -0.8467616 3.067857 -5.397824 0.8130241
## 19 -5.7068728 -0.8467616 3.067857 -5.397824 0.8130241
## 20 -5.9721487 -0.8467616 3.067857 -5.397824 0.8130241
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## High      -6.488997 -0.8467616 3.067857 -5.397824 0.8130241
## Low       1.280003 -0.8467616 3.067857 -5.397824 0.8130241
## Medium  -1.630734 -0.8467616 3.067857 -5.397824 0.8130241
## Water   -2.075734 -0.8467616 3.067857 -5.397824 0.8130241
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      corr      zygo      lev      mass
## Bitter  -9.799154 -0.8467616 3.067857 -5.397824 0.8130241
## Sweet    5.341423 -0.8467616 3.067857 -5.397824 0.8130241
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(LMRTModRI4, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(LMRTModRI4)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## corr  1 3515.7  3515.7  20.0143
```

```
## zygo 1 182.8 182.8 1.0404
## lev 1 2051.9 2051.9 11.6812
## mass 1 18.2 18.2 0.1038
```

Standardised scores

Tasting Block (zscore)

```
#Tasting Block (zscore)
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Emptying Screen
```

```
zLMTEModRI4 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTEModRI4
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula:
```

```
## zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
```

```
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 358.8949 386.0504 -170.4474 340.8949 142
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 0.2195
## intensity (Intercept) 0.3267
## content (Intercept) 0.4766
## Residual 0.6891
```

```
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
```

```
## Fixed Effects:
```

```
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## -0.07633 -0.36701 0.11246 -0.10109 -0.08138
```

```
confint(zLMTEModRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
##          2.5 %    97.5 %
## .sig01  0.0000000 0.34329570
## .sig02  0.0000000 0.55034917
## .sig03  0.0000000 0.75734328
## .sigma  0.5984976 0.76682987
## (Intercept) -0.8154575 0.66963039
## zcorr      -0.7600006 0.01729164
## zzygo      -0.1637231 0.38374332
## zlev       -0.3438929 0.12993119
## zmass      -0.3797204 0.20654791
```

```
coef(zLMTEModRI4)
```

```

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## 1  0.003244403 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 2 -0.137724226 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 3  0.101696565 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 4 -0.088906727 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 5 -0.266443283 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 6 -0.041909784 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 7 -0.257660983 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 8  0.199793421 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 9 -0.189740399 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 10 -0.084652702 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 12 -0.154311931 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 13 -0.026429737 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 14 -0.133407247 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 15 -0.094420361 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 16  0.140467217 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 17  0.196718365 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 18 -0.184864942 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 19 -0.248080558 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## 20 -0.183582706 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## High -0.51760738 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## Low  0.22472153 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## Medium -0.07986624 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## Water 0.06744354 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## Bitter -0.5222811 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
## Sweet  0.3696268 -0.36701 0.112458 -0.1010937 -0.08137925
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTEModRI4, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMTEModRI4)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr  1  4.4314   4.4314   9.3326
## zzygo  1  0.0376   0.0376   0.0792
## zlev   1  0.3228   0.3228   0.6797
## zmass  1  0.1424   0.1424   0.2999
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Swirling Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Swirling Screen
```

```
zLMTSModRI4 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTSModRI4
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula:
## zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 355.4304 382.5859 -168.7152  337.4304     142
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.2255
## intensity (Intercept) 0.2660
```

```

## content (Intercept) 0.4727
## Residual 0.6823
## Number of obs: 151, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## -0.06455 -0.10961 0.13232 -0.12662 -0.28517

confint(zLMTSModRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.00000000 0.36369697
## .sig02 0.00000000 0.45674733
## .sig03 0.00000000 0.75875899
## .sigma 0.59003709 0.75276570
## (Intercept) -0.78075512 0.66028420
## zcorr -0.30028348 0.07698347
## zzygo 0.01185853 0.24465121
## zlev -0.31966841 0.06950538
## zmass -0.80525049 0.25981656

coef(zLMTSModRI4)

## $ptp
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## 1 0.054934423 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 2 -0.120688124 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 3 0.150947567 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 4 -0.085635323 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 5 -0.311442189 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 6 -0.042984837 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 7 -0.099458868 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 8 0.254207078 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 9 -0.169259316 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 10 -0.288686334 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 12 -0.118147202 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 13 -0.003366979 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 14 -0.092952411 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 15 -0.037843850 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 16 0.037626341 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 17 0.203833879 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 18 -0.202312474 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 19 -0.205272150 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## 20 -0.149865352 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## High -0.409271722 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## Low 0.194306919 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## Medium -0.036898183 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694

```

```
## Water -0.006319355 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
##
## $content
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## Bitter -0.5129528 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
## Sweet 0.3838616 -0.1096094 0.132322 -0.1266232 -0.2851694
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTSModRI4, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMTSModRI4)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 4.4064  4.4064  9.4658
## zzygo 1 1.4906  1.4906  3.2020
## zlev  1 0.8572  0.8572  1.8414
## zmass 1 0.5317  0.5317  1.1421
```

```
cat("Tasting Block Thinking Screen")
```

```
## Tasting Block Thinking Screen
```

```
zLMTTModRI4 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting, REML = FALSE)
zLMTTModRI4
```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula:
## zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
## AIC      BIC      logLik  deviance  df.resid
## 352.4542 379.6097 -167.2271 334.4542    142
## Random effects:
## Groups      Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp          (Intercept) 0.2155
## intensity    (Intercept) 0.2551
## content      (Intercept) 0.4815
## Residual                    0.6772
## Number of obs: 151, groups:  ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## -0.20630      -0.08326      0.17434      -0.28796      -0.31441

confint(zLMTTModRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

##              2.5 %      97.5 %
## .sig01      0.00000000 0.35217773
## .sig02      0.00000000 0.43755065
## .sig03      0.00000000 0.80532196
## .sigma      0.58579039 0.75038341
## (Intercept) -0.95587134 0.54352555
## zcorr      -0.32397720 0.16540323
## zzygo      0.01782481 0.33162728
## zlev      -0.65110580 0.07052392
## zmass      -1.08868832 0.45689411

coef(zLMTTModRI4)

## $ptp
## (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## 1 -0.10141614 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 2 -0.19608011 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 3 -0.03657546 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 4 -0.25650711 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 5 -0.44886493 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 6 -0.18509984 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 7 -0.24946743 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 8 0.09574923 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 9 -0.29505796 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 10 -0.38416433 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 12 -0.21045623 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 13 -0.11283584 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 14 -0.24340797 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 15 -0.24043513 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063

```

```
## 16 -0.08287156 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 17 0.04039341 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 18 -0.33204994 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 19 -0.34223558 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## 20 -0.33823485 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## High    -0.5374727 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## Low      0.0347977 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## Medium  -0.1731849 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## Water   -0.1493227 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## Bitter  -0.6651510 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
## Sweet    0.2525596 -0.08326091 0.1743439 -0.2879606 -0.3144063
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMTTModRI4, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMTTModRI4)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

```
## zcorr 1 5.4748 5.4748 11.9384
## zzygo 1 1.3371 1.3371 2.9157
## zlev 1 1.6495 1.6495 3.5968
## zmass 1 0.3037 0.3037 0.6623
```

Tasting and Rating Block (zscore)

```
#Tasting and Rating Block (zscore)
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Emptying Screen
```

```
zLMREModRI4 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity) , data = EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMREModRI4
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
```

```
## Formula:
```

```
## zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
```

```
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 360.0045 387.2194 -171.0022 342.0045 143
```

```
## Random effects:
```

```
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 0.1888
## intensity (Intercept) 0.3421
## content (Intercept) 0.4339
## Residual 0.6921
```

```
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
```

```
## Fixed Effects:
```

```
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## 0.006357 -0.088977 0.284539 -0.259197 -0.523929
```

```
confint(zLMREModRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)
```

```
## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...
```

```
## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.00000000 0.31817586
## .sig02 0.00000000 0.56183499
## .sig03 0.00000000 0.72133683
## .sigma 0.60131842 0.76898445
## (Intercept) -0.72719132 0.70666371
## zcorr -0.34374414 0.16946517
## zzygo 0.08544305 0.49451982
## zlev -0.43234683 -0.09059469
## zmass -1.21148003 0.13632639
```

```
coef(zLMREModRI4)
```

```

## $ptp
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## 1  0.0889861266 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 2  0.0085017391 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 3  0.1369532541 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 4 -0.0290891154 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 5  0.0058863699 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 6 -0.0003025486 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 7 -0.2018913394 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 8  0.2111039408 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 9 -0.1224089067 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 10 -0.0230441885 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 12 -0.0243118637 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 13  0.0697339028 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 14 -0.0008913324 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 15 -0.0122608645 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 16  0.1429581575 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 17  0.2156753603 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 18 -0.1198657205 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 19 -0.1144331354 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## 20 -0.1105097186 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## High  -0.48441477 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## Low   0.28247482 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## Medium 0.07198185 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## Water  0.15538761 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## Bitter -0.3937810 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
## Sweet  0.4064957 -0.08897729 0.2845385 -0.2591967 -0.523929
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMREModRI4, id = 0.05)

```



```
anova(zLMREModRI4)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr 1 2.3064  2.3064  4.8153
## zzygo 1 0.2078  0.2078  0.4338
## zlev  1 3.9644  3.9644  8.2769
## zmass 1 1.1587  1.1587  2.4192
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Swirling Screen
```

```
zLMRSMoRI4 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), data = EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMRSMoRI4
```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula:
## zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
##      AIC      BIC    logLik deviance df.resid
## 349.8384 377.0533 -165.9192  331.8384     143
## Random effects:
## Groups   Name      Std.Dev.
## ptp      (Intercept) 0.1843
## intensity (Intercept) 0.2532
```

```

## content (Intercept) 0.4371
## Residual 0.6722
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## 0.03174 -0.07780 0.08734 -0.23657 -0.14946

confint(zLMRSMoRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.00000000 0.31235136
## .sig02 0.00000000 0.43020600
## .sig03 0.00000000 0.72016789
## .sigma 0.58398360 0.74311366
## (Intercept) -0.63617595 0.68297413
## zcorr -0.21200884 0.05901696
## zzygo -0.02374562 0.20167283
## zlev -0.40377918 -0.06780586
## zmass -0.48755043 0.19421261

coef(zLMRSMoRI4)

## $ptp
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## 1 0.116011655 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 2 -0.044201146 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 3 0.192107776 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 4 0.018547514 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 5 -0.110197189 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 6 0.046606509 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 7 0.061970335 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 8 0.272645260 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 9 -0.082372162 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 10 -0.137732837 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 12 -0.046665018 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 13 0.075032560 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 14 -0.013006044 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 15 0.081979206 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 16 0.151673038 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 17 0.173219281 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 18 -0.081216069 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 19 -0.064622029 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## 20 -0.006646754 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
##
## $intensity
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## High -0.2959568 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## Low 0.2735432 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## Medium 0.0467861 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561

```

```
## Water    0.1026030 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## Bitter -0.3818829 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
## Sweet   0.4453706 -0.07779522 0.08734332 -0.2365672 -0.1494561
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMRSMoRI4, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMRSMoRI4)
```

```
## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
## zcorr  1  6.4905   6.4905 14.3622
## zzygo  1  0.1448   0.1448  0.3205
## zlev   1  4.1852   4.1852  9.2610
## zmass  1  0.3305   0.3305  0.7314
```

```
cat("Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen")
```

```
## Tasting and Rating Block Thinking Screen
```

```
zLMRTModRI4 <- lmer(zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1|ptp) + (1|content) + (1|intensity), data = EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating, REML = FALSE)
zLMRTModRI4
```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood ['lmerMod']
## Formula:
## zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## (1 | intensity)
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
## AIC BIC logLik deviance df.resid
## 357.4602 384.6751 -169.7301 339.4602 143
## Random effects:
## Groups Name Std.Dev.
## ptp (Intercept) 0.2709
## intensity (Intercept) 0.1870
## content (Intercept) 0.4082
## Residual 0.6792
## Number of obs: 152, groups: ptp, 19; intensity, 4; content, 2
## Fixed Effects:
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## -0.18006 -0.06512 0.14194 -0.47919 0.10484

confint(zLMRTModRI4, method = "boot", nsim = 5000)

## Computing bootstrap confidence intervals ...

## 2.5 % 97.5 %
## .sig01 0.00000000 0.4088121
## .sig02 0.00000000 0.3386220
## .sig03 0.00000000 0.6792915
## .sigma 0.59032139 0.7551494
## (Intercept) -0.80511544 0.4441720
## zcorr -0.25717648 0.1246138
## zzygo -0.02500108 0.3051397
## zlev -0.76317488 -0.1833992
## zmass -0.54360445 0.7347345

coef(zLMRTModRI4)

## $ptp
## (Intercept) zcorr zzygo zlev zmass
## 1 -0.046376056 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 2 -0.286894032 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 3 -0.016515134 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 4 -0.302940376 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 5 -0.478404203 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 6 -0.178827279 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 7 -0.204443421 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 8 0.265779141 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 9 -0.317415024 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 10 -0.324547542 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 12 -0.203813608 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 13 0.084065968 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 14 -0.292082686 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406
## 15 -0.200874805 -0.06511732 0.141936 -0.4791896 0.1048406

```

```
## 16  0.179346974 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
## 17 -0.006625444 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
## 18 -0.360297869 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
## 19 -0.358304766 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
## 20 -0.371900202 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
##
## $intensity
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## High  -0.3983887136 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
## Low   -0.0002262776 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
## Medium -0.1494020086 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
## Water -0.1722083399 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
##
## $content
##      (Intercept)      zcorr      zzygo      zlev      zmass
## Bitter -0.5680348 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
## Sweet   0.2079221 -0.06511732  0.141936 -0.4791896  0.1048406
##
## attr(,"class")
## [1] "coef.mer"

qqmath(zLMRTModRI4, id = 0.05)
```



```
anova(zLMRTModRI4)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value
```

```
## zcorr 1 9.2342 9.2342 20.0143
## zzygo 1 0.4800 0.4800 1.0404
## zlev 1 5.3895 5.3895 11.6812
## zmass 1 0.0479 0.0479 0.1038
```

Model Comparison: random effect: ptp only

Null model = random effect only (ptp)

Full model = random effect + fixed effects (corr+lev+zygo)

raw data

```
# raw data
```

```
anova(LMTEModRandomNull, LMTEModRI)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
```

```
## Models:
```

```
## LMTEModRandomNull: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
```

```
## LMTEModRI: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
```

```
##           Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
```

```
## LMTEModRandomNull 3 1323.0 1332.1 -658.53  1317.0
```

```
## LMTEModRI          6 1293.5 1311.6 -640.74  1281.5 35.582    3
```

```
##           Pr(>Chisq)
```

```
## LMTEModRandomNull
```

```
## LMTEModRI          9.18e-08 ***
```

```
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
anova(LMTSModRandomNull, LMTSModRI)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
```

```
## Models:
```

```
## LMTSModRandomNull: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
```

```
## LMTSModRI: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
```

```
##           Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
```

```
## LMTSModRandomNull 3 1323.3 1332.4 -658.66  1317.3
```

```
## LMTSModRI          6 1290.0 1308.1 -638.98  1278.0 39.368    3
```

```
##           Pr(>Chisq)
```

```
## LMTSModRandomNull
```

```
## LMTSModRI          1.45e-08 ***
```

```
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
anova(LMTTModRandomNull, LMTTModRI)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
```

```
## Models:
```

```
## LMTTModRandomNull: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
```

```
## LMTTModRI: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
```

```
##           Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
```

```

## LMTTModRandomNull  3 1323.3 1332.4 -658.66  1317.3
## LMTTModRI          6 1289.0 1307.1 -638.51  1277.0 40.31      3
##
## Pr(>Chisq)
## LMTTModRandomNull
## LMTTModRI          9.159e-09 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(LMREModRandomNull, LMREModRI)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
## Models:
## LMREModRandomNull: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## LMREModRI: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
##
##      Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## LMREModRandomNull  3 1330.0 1339.1 -662.00  1324.0
## LMREModRI          6 1296.9 1315.0 -642.44  1284.9 39.123    3
##
## Pr(>Chisq)
## LMREModRandomNull
## LMREModRI          1.635e-08 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(LMRSMoModRandomNull, LMRSMoModRI)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
## Models:
## LMRSMoModRandomNull: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## LMRSMoModRI: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
##
##      Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## LMRSMoModRandomNull  3 1331.1 1340.2 -662.57  1325.1
## LMRSMoModRI          6 1286.2 1304.3 -637.09  1274.2 50.957    3
##
## Pr(>Chisq)
## LMRSMoModRandomNull
## LMRSMoModRI          4.997e-11 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(LMRTModRandomNull, LMRTModRI)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
## Models:
## LMRTModRandomNull: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## LMRTModRI: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp)
##
##      Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## LMRTModRandomNull  3 1334.2 1343.3 -664.09  1328.2
## LMRTModRI          6 1288.2 1306.3 -638.09  1276.2 52.009    3
##
## Pr(>Chisq)
## LMRTModRandomNull
## LMRTModRI          2.982e-11 ***

```

```

## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

standardised (zscores)
# standardised (zscores)
anova(zLMTEModRandomNull, zLMTEModRI)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
## Models:
## zLMTEModRandomNull: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## zLMTEModRI: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
##           Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMTEModRandomNull  3 425.80 434.85 -209.90  419.80
## zLMTEModRI          6 396.22 414.32 -192.11  384.22 35.582    3
##           Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMTEModRandomNull
## zLMTEModRI          9.18e-08 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(zLMTSModRandomNull, zLMTSModRI)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
## Models:
## zLMTSModRandomNull: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## zLMTSModRI: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
##           Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMTSModRandomNull  3 426.07 435.12 -210.03  420.07
## zLMTSModRI          6 392.70 410.80 -190.35  380.70 39.368    3
##           Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMTSModRandomNull
## zLMTSModRI          1.45e-08 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(zLMTTModRandomNull, zLMTTModRI)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
## Models:
## zLMTTModRandomNull: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## zLMTTModRI: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
##           Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMTTModRandomNull  3 426.07 435.12 -210.03  420.07
## zLMTTModRI          6 391.76 409.86 -189.88  379.76 40.31    3
##           Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMTTModRandomNull
## zLMTTModRI          9.159e-09 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(zLMREModRandomNull, zLMREModRI)

```

```

## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
## Models:
## zLMREModRandomNull: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## zLMREModRI: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
##           Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMREModRandomNull  3 426.81 435.88 -210.40  420.81
## zLMREModRI          6 393.68 411.83 -190.84  381.68 39.123    3
##           Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMREModRandomNull
## zLMREModRI          1.635e-08 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(zLMRSMoRandomNull, zLMRSMoRI)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
## Models:
## zLMRSMoRandomNull: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## zLMRSMoRI: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
##           Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMRSMoRandomNull  3 427.94 437.01 -210.97  421.94
## zLMRSMoRI          6 382.99 401.13 -185.49  370.99 50.957    3
##           Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMRSMoRandomNull
## zLMRSMoRI          4.997e-11 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(zLMRTMoRandomNull, zLMRTMoRI)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
## Models:
## zLMRTMoRandomNull: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp)
## zLMRTMoRI: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp)
##           Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMRTMoRandomNull  3 430.99 440.07 -212.50  424.99
## zLMRTMoRI          6 384.98 403.13 -186.49  372.98 52.009    3
##           Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMRTMoRandomNull
## zLMRTMoRI          2.982e-11 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

Model Comparison: Random effect: ptp + content + concentration

Null model = random effects (ptp, content, concentration)

Full models = random effect + fixed effects (corr+lev+zzygo)

raw data

```

# raw data
anova(LMTEModRandomNull3, LMTEModRI3, LMTEModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
## Models:
## LMTEModRandomNull3: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## LMTEModRI3: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | int
ensity)
## LMTEModRI4: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## LMTEModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##
##          Df      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## LMTEModRandomNull3  5 1258.0 1273.1 -624.01  1248.0
## LMTEModRI3          8 1254.4 1278.6 -619.21  1238.4 9.5951      3
## LMTEModRI4          9 1256.2 1283.3 -619.07  1238.2 0.2727      1
##
##          Pr(>Chisq)
## LMTEModRandomNull3
## LMTEModRI3          0.02234 *
## LMTEModRI4          0.60152
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(LMTSModRandomNull3, LMTSModRI3, LMTSModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
## Models:
## LMTSModRandomNull3: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## LMTSModRI3: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | int
ensity)
## LMTSModRI4: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## LMTSModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##
##          Df      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## LMTSModRandomNull3  5 1258.8 1273.8 -624.37  1248.8
## LMTSModRI3          8 1251.8 1276.0 -617.91  1235.8 12.9273      3
## LMTSModRI4          9 1252.7 1279.8 -617.34  1234.7  1.1352      1
##
##          Pr(>Chisq)
## LMTSModRandomNull3
## LMTSModRI3          0.004796 **
## LMTSModRI4          0.286675
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(LMTTModRandomNull3, LMTTModRI3, LMTTModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
## Models:
## LMTTModRandomNull3: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## LMTTModRI3: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | int
ensity)
## LMTTModRI4: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +

```

```

## LMTTModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##                Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## LMTTModRandomNull3  5 1258.8 1273.8 -624.37  1248.8
## LMTTModRI3        8 1248.4 1272.5 -616.18  1232.4 16.3795    3
## LMTTModRI4        9 1249.7 1276.9 -615.85  1231.7  0.6592    1
##                Pr(>Chisq)
## LMTTModRandomNull3
## LMTTModRI3        0.0009479 ***
## LMTTModRI4        0.4168422
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(LMREModRandomNull3, LMREModRI3, LMREModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
## Models:
## LMREModRandomNull3: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## LMREModRI3: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | int
ensity)
## LMREModRI4: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## LMREModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##                Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## LMREModRandomNull3  5 1270.2 1285.3 -630.10  1260.2
## LMREModRI3        8 1263.5 1287.7 -623.77  1247.5 12.6729    3
## LMREModRI4        9 1263.2 1290.4 -622.60  1245.2  2.3318    1
##                Pr(>Chisq)
## LMREModRandomNull3
## LMREModRI3        0.0054 **
## LMREModRI4        0.1268
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(LMRModRandomNull3, LMRModRI3, LMRModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
## Models:
## LMRModRandomNull3: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## LMRModRI3: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | int
ensity)
## LMRModRI4: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## LMRModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##                Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## LMRModRandomNull3  5 1266.8 1282.0 -628.42  1256.8
## LMRModRI3        8 1251.8 1276.0 -617.88  1235.8 21.073    3
## LMRModRI4        9 1253.0 1280.2 -617.52  1235.0  0.729    1
##                Pr(>Chisq)
## LMRModRandomNull3
## LMRModRI3        0.0001017 ***
## LMRModRI4        0.3932170
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```
anova(LMRTModRandomNull3, LMRTModRI3, LMRTModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
## Models:
## LMRTModRandomNull3: LAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## LMRTModRI3: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## LMRTModRI4: LAM ~ corr + zygo + lev + mass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## LMRTModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##              Df      AIC      BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## LMRTModRandomNull3  5 1280.1 1295.3 -635.07  1270.1
## LMRTModRI3          8 1258.8 1283.0 -621.38  1242.8 27.3796      3
## LMRTModRI4          9 1260.7 1287.9 -621.33  1242.7  0.1029      1
##              Pr(>Chisq)
## LMRTModRandomNull3
## LMRTModRI3          4.901e-06 ***
## LMRTModRI4          0.7483
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

standardised (zscores)

```
# standardised (zscores)
anova(zLMTEModRandomNull3, zLMTEModRI3, zLMTEModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Tasting
## Models:
## zLMTEModRandomNull3: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
## zLMTEModRI3: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1
## zLMTEModRI3:      intensity)
## zLMTEModRI4: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) +
## zLMTEModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##              Df      AIC      BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMTEModRandomNull3  5 360.76 375.85 -175.38  350.76
## zLMTEModRI3          8 357.17 381.31 -170.58  341.17 9.5951      3
## zLMTEModRI4          9 358.89 386.05 -170.45  340.89 0.2727      1
##              Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMTEModRandomNull3
## zLMTEModRI3          0.02234 *
## zLMTEModRI4          0.60152
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
anova(zLMTSModRandomNull3, zLMTSModRI3, zLMTSModRI4)
```

```
## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Tasting
## Models:
## zLMTSModRandomNull3: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity)
```

```

)
## zLMTSModRI3: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1
|
## zLMTSModRI3:      intensity)
## zLMTSModRI4: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | conten
t) +
## zLMTSModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##
##          Df      AIC      BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMTSModRandomNull3  5 361.49 376.58 -175.75  351.49
## zLMTSModRI3          8 354.57 378.70 -169.28  338.57 12.9273      3
## zLMTSModRI4          9 355.43 382.59 -168.72  337.43  1.1352      1
##
##          Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMTSModRandomNull3
## zLMTSModRI3          0.004796 **
## zLMTSModRI4          0.286675
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(zLMTTModRandomNull3, zLMTTModRI3, zLMTTModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Tasting
## Models:
## zLMTTModRandomNull3: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity
)
## zLMTTModRI3: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1
|
## zLMTTModRI3:      intensity)
## zLMTTModRI4: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | conten
t) +
## zLMTTModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##
##          Df      AIC      BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMTTModRandomNull3  5 361.49 376.58 -175.75  351.49
## zLMTTModRI3          8 351.11 375.25 -167.56  335.11 16.3795      3
## zLMTTModRI4          9 352.45 379.61 -167.23  334.45  0.6592      1
##
##          Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMTTModRandomNull3
## zLMTTModRI3          0.0009479 ***
## zLMTTModRI4          0.4168422
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(zLMREModRandomNull3, zLMREModRI3, zLMREModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Emptying.Rating
## Models:
## zLMREModRandomNull3: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity
)
## zLMREModRI3: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1
|
## zLMREModRI3:      intensity)
## zLMREModRI4: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | conten

```

```

t) +
## zLMREModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##                Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMREModRandomNull3  5 367.01 382.13 -178.50   357.01
## zLMREModRI3         8 360.34 384.53 -172.17   344.34 12.6729     3
## zLMREModRI4         9 360.00 387.22 -171.00   342.00  2.3318     1
##                Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMREModRandomNull3
## zLMREModRI3         0.0054 **
## zLMREModRI4         0.1268
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(zLMRModRandomNull3, zLMRModRI3, zLMRModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Swirling.Rating
## Models:
## zLMRModRandomNull3: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity
)
## zLMRModRI3: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1
|
## zLMRModRI3:      intensity)
## zLMRModRI4: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | conten
t) +
## zLMRModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##                Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMRModRandomNull3  5 363.64 378.76 -176.82   353.64
## zLMRModRI3         8 348.57 372.76 -166.28   332.57 21.073     3
## zLMRModRI4         9 349.84 377.05 -165.92   331.84  0.729     1
##                Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMRModRandomNull3
## zLMRModRI3         0.0001017 ***
## zLMRModRI4         0.3932170
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

anova(zLMRTModRandomNull3, zLMRTModRI3, zLMRTModRI4)

## Data: EMGMLMave.Thinking.Rating
## Models:
## zLMRTModRandomNull3: zLAM ~ 1 + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1 | intensity
)
## zLMRTModRI3: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + (1 | ptp) + (1 | content) + (1
|
## zLMRTModRI3:      intensity)
## zLMRTModRI4: zLAM ~ zcorr + zzygo + zlev + zmass + (1 | ptp) + (1 | conten
t) +
## zLMRTModRI4:      (1 | intensity)
##                Df    AIC    BIC  logLik deviance  Chisq Chi Df
## zLMRTModRandomNull3  5 376.94 392.06 -183.47   366.94
## zLMRTModRI3         8 355.56 379.75 -169.78   339.56 27.3796     3

```

```

## zLMRTModRI4          9 357.46 384.68 -169.73   339.46  0.1029    1
##                               Pr(>Chisq)
## zLMRTModRandomNull3
## zLMRTModRI3          4.901e-06 ***
## zLMRTModRI4          0.7483
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

Parametric Percentile Bootstrapped 95%CI

Parametric bootstrapping with robust extraction using percentiles

confint.merMod(**MODEL.FIT**, method = "boot", level=.95, boot.type = "perc", nsim=10000)

Raw data

```

=====
      fit lower upper  names      analysis      block      phase
-----
3  -2.91 -4.93 -0.84  Levator  Rating:Emptying  Tasting and Rating Emptying
2  4.99  0.67  9.24  Zygomaticus Rating:Emptying  Tasting and Rating Emptying
1  -2.89 -5.46 -0.36  Corrugator Rating:Emptying  Tasting and Rating Emptying
31 -2.81 -4.64 -0.96  Levator  Rating:Swirling  Tasting and Rating Swirling
21  1.67 -0.69  3.95  Zygomaticus Rating:Swirling  Tasting and Rating Swirling
11 -1.14 -2.91  0.55  Corrugator Rating:Swirling  Tasting and Rating Swirling
32 -5.22 -8.28 -2.17  Levator  Rating:Thinking  Tasting and Rating Thinking
22  3.17 -0.34  6.72  Zygomaticus Rating:Thinking  Tasting and Rating Thinking
12 -0.82 -3.26  1.61  Corrugator Rating:Thinking  Tasting and Rating Thinking
33 -1.09 -3.71  1.65  Levator  Tasting:Emptying  Tasting Only Emptying
23  2.12 -4.15  8.02  Zygomaticus Tasting:Emptying  Tasting Only Emptying
13 -5.70 -9.57 -1.84  Corrugator Tasting:Emptying  Tasting Only Emptying
34 -1.46 -3.62  0.74  Levator  Tasting:Swirling  Tasting Only Swirling
24  2.43  0.10  4.78  Zygomaticus Tasting:Swirling  Tasting Only Swirling
14 -1.87 -4.24  0.50  Corrugator Tasting:Swirling  Tasting Only Swirling
35 -3.66 -7.61  0.21  Levator  Tasting:Thinking  Tasting Only Thinking
25  3.52  0.22  6.94  Zygomaticus Tasting:Thinking  Tasting Only Thinking
15 -1.25 -4.36  1.96  Corrugator Tasting:Thinking  Tasting Only Thinking
-----

```

Standardised models (z-score)

```

=====
      fit lower upper  names      analysis      block      phase
-----
3  -0.26 -0.44 -0.07  Levator  Rating:Emptying  Tasting and Rating Emptying
2  0.23  0.03  0.43  Zygomaticus Rating:Emptying  Tasting and Rating Emptying
1  -0.22 -0.42 -0.03  Corrugator Rating:Emptying  Tasting and Rating Emptying

```

31	-0.25	-0.41	-0.09	Levator	Rating:Swirling	Tasting and Rating	Swirling
21	0.08	-0.03	0.18	Zygomaticus	Rating:Swirling	Tasting and Rating	Swirling
11	-0.09	-0.22	0.05	Corrugator	Rating:Swirling	Tasting and Rating	Swirling
32	-0.46	-0.74	-0.19	Levator	Rating:Thinking	Tasting and Rating	Thinking
22	0.15	-0.02	0.31	Zygomaticus	Rating:Thinking	Tasting and Rating	Thinking
12	-0.06	-0.25	0.13	Corrugator	Rating:Thinking	Tasting and Rating	Thinking
33	-0.10	-0.34	0.14	Levator	Tasting:Emptying	Tasting Only	Emptying
23	0.10	-0.17	0.38	Zygomaticus	Tasting:Emptying	Tasting Only	Emptying
13	-0.44	-0.73	-0.15	Corrugator	Tasting:Emptying	Tasting Only	Emptying
34	-0.13	-0.32	0.06	Levator	Tasting:Swirling	Tasting Only	Swirling
24	0.11	0.002	0.22	Zygomaticus	Tasting:Swirling	Tasting Only	Swirling
14	-0.14	-0.32	0.03	Corrugator	Tasting:Swirling	Tasting Only	Swirling
35	-0.32	-0.68	0.03	Levator	Tasting:Thinking	Tasting Only	Thinking
25	0.16	0.01	0.32	Zygomaticus	Tasting:Thinking	Tasting Only	Thinking
15	-0.10	-0.34	0.15	Corrugator	Tasting:Thinking	Tasting Only	Thinking

CDFs for full models (raw data)

Tasting Block (raw)

Emptying

```
LMTEModRI3.theta <- profile(LMTEModRI3)
densityplot(LMTEModRI3.theta)
```



```
# Swirling
LMTSModRI3.theta <- profile(LMTSModRI3)
densityplot(LMTSModRI3.theta)
```



```
# Thinking
LMTTModRI3.theta <- profile(LMTTModRI3)
densityplot(LMTTModRI3.theta)
```


Tasting and Rating Block (Raw)

```
# Emptying
```

```
LMREModRI3.theta <- profile(LMREModRI3)
```

```
densityplot(LMREModRI3.theta)
```



```
# Swirling
```

```
LMRSMODRI3.theta <- profile(LMRSMODRI3)
```

```
densityplot(LMRSMODRI3.theta)
```


Thinking

```
LMRTModRI3.theta <- profile(LMRTModRI3)
densityplot(LMRTModRI3.theta)
```


CDFs for full models (zscore data)

Tasting Block (zscore)

Emptying

```
zLMTEModRI3.theta <- profile(zLMTEModRI3)
densityplot(zLMTEModRI3.theta)
```



```
# Swirling
zLMTSMoRI3.theta <- profile(zLMTSMoRI3)
densityplot(zLMTSMoRI3.theta)
```



```
# Thinking
zLMTTModRI3.theta <- profile(zLMTTModRI3)
densityplot(zLMTTModRI3.theta)
```


Tasting and Rating Block (zscore)

```
# Emptying
zLMREModRI3.theta <- profile(zLMREModRI3)
densityplot(zLMREModRI3.theta)
```



```
# Swirling
zLMRSMoRI3.theta <- profile(zLMRSMoRI3)
densityplot(zLMRSMoRI3.theta)
```



```
# Thinking  
zLMRTModRI3.theta <- profile(zLMRTModRI3)  
densityplot(zLMRTModRI3.theta)
```

